

The Food Safety Market: An SME-powered industrial data platform to boost the competitiveness of European food certification

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COORDINATOR	Nikos Manouselis
ADDRESS	110 Pentelis Str., Marousi, GR15126, Greece
REPLY TO	nikosm@agroknow.com
PHONE	+30 210 6897 905
EU PROJECT OFFICER	Stefano Bertolo
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RESPONSIBLE AUTHOR	Dimitris Fotakidis (Agroknow)
REPLY TO	dimitris.fotakidis@agroknow.com
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CONTRIBUTORS	All partners
REVIEWER	Tima Out Anwana, Lukas Faymann (UNIVIE)

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PARTNERS		CONTACT
Agroknow IKE (Agroknow, Greece)		Nikos Manouselis (Agroknow) nikosm@agroknow.com
SIRMA AI EAD (SAI, Bulgaria)		Zlatina Marinova (SAI) zlatina.marinova@ontotext.com
GIOUMPITEK MELETI SCHEDIASMOS YLOPOIISI KAI POLISI ERGON PLIROFORIKIS ETAIREIA PERIORISMENIS EFTHYNIS (UBITECH, Greece)		Danai Vergeti (UBITECH) vergetid@ubitech.eu
AGRIVI DOO ZA PROIZVODNJU, TRGOVINU I USLUGE (Agrivi d.o.o., Croatia)		Filip Gerin (Agrivi d.o.o.) filip.gerin@agrivi.com
PROSPEH, POSLOVNE STORITVE IN DIGITALNE RESITVE DOO (PROSPEH DOO, Slovenia)		Martina Poberaj (PROSPEH DOO) martina.poberaj@tracelabs.io
UNIVERSITAT WIEN (UNIVIE, Austria)		Tima Anwana (UNIVIE) tima.anwana@univie.ac.at
STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH (WFSR, Netherlands)		Yamine Bouzembrak (WFSR) yamine.bouzembrak@wur.nl
TUV- AUSTRIA ELLAS MONOPROSOPI ETAIREIA PERIORISMENIS EUTHYNIS (TUV AU HELLAS, Greece)		Kostas Mavropoulos (TUV AU HELLAS) konstantinos.mavropoulos@tuv.at
TUV AUSTRIA ROMANIA SRL (TUV AU ROMANIA, Romania)		George Gheorghiu (TUV AU Romania) george.gheorghiu@tuv.at
VALORITALIA SOCIETA PER LA CERTIFICAZIONE DELLE QUALITA'E DELLE PRODUZIONI VITIVINICOLE ITALIANE SRL (VALORITALIA, Italy)		Francesca Romero (Valoritalia) francesca.romero@valoritalia.it
TUV AUSTRIA CYPRUS (TUV AU CYPRUS, Cyprus)		Sousanna Charalambidou (TUV AU CYPRUS) sousanna.charalambidou@tuv.at

ACRONYMS LIST

TheFSM	The Food Safety Market
BR(s)	Business Requirement(s)
BSC(s)	Business Scenario(s)
CB	Certification Body
D	Deliverable
FG(s)	Focus Group(s)
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
rBRc	reference BR category
T	Task
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The current document, entitled “Published Project Report”, constitutes the first of the two project reports of TheFSM project. This deliverable presents the project’s vision and ambition and summarises the project’s advancements achieved during the first 18 months of its execution.

More specifically, the document provides the 2nd version of business, data, legal and technical requirements under the TheFSM project, which will be the basis of the main functionalities of TheFSM platform and applications. It reports the process and outcomes of agile and iterative development of the software applications, namely Food Inspector Application, FOODAKAI 2.0 application and the Agrivi 2.0 application and presents with more details the information gathered about the interfaces required for the implementation of the integrated platform by defining the communication between the components. Furthermore, presents TheFSM backbone infrastructure that will support the implementation and deployment of TheFSM platform, document the technology stack of TheFSM infrastructure that enable the platform’s scalability, robustness and high performance and presents platform’s prototype. Additionally, the initial TheFSM Marketplace mock-ups are also presented.

Moreover, pilot groups, pilot sites and pilot schedule are incorporated. Finally, this report describes the dissemination and communication tools and channels that were used to promote the key messages and the produced by the consortium material, and the collaborations and synergies in the domain of food safety and fraud.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
1. INTRODUCTION	13
1.1. Scope.....	13
1.2. Audience.....	13
1.3. TheFSM Mission, Vision & Values.....	13
1.4. Structure.....	14
1.5. Relation to Other Deliverables.....	15
2. PROJECT REQUIREMENTS	16
2.1. Business Scenarios.....	16
2.2. Business Requirements Grouped in Users Stories.....	18
2.3. Requirements' Results.....	19
2.3.1. Business requirements.....	19
2.3.2. Legal requirements.....	20
2.3.3. Technical requirements.....	22
2.3.4. Data requirements.....	23
3. APPLICATIONS	24
3.1. Agile Applications Development Iterative Process.....	24
3.2. Outcomes of Agile Development Process.....	26
3.3. Food Inspector Application.....	26
3.3.1. Developments status	26
3.4. FOODAKAI 2.0.....	33
3.4.1. Developments status	34
3.5. AGRIVI 2.0.....	40
3.5.1. Developments status	40
3.6. TheFSM Applications Interface.....	43
3.6.1 Data Exchange Scenarios.....	43
4. THEFSM PLATFORM	46
4.1. Backbone Infrastructure.....	46

4.2.	Technology Stack.....	47
4.2.1.	Authorization and Access Control Engine:.....	47
4.2.2.	Data Curation and Semantic Enrichment	49
4.2.3.	Data Market Modelling	50
4.3.	TheFSM Platform Prototype	51
4.3.1.	Administrator.....	51
4.3.2.	Security Layer	53
4.3.3.	Data Management Layer.....	57
4.3.4.	Design principles.....	59
5.	THEFSM DATA MARKET PLACE	64
5.1.	TheFSM Data Market.....	64
5.1.1.	Welcome page.....	64
5.1.2.	Dataset providers.....	65
5.1.3.	Thematic categories of dataset packages	66
5.1.4.	Creation of custom data package	67
5.1.5.	Selection of datasets from categories and providers	68
5.1.6.	Advanced filtered dataset search	69
5.1.7.	Dataset sampling and purchase.....	70
5.1.8.	Ordering a dataset	71
5.1.9.	Dataset's metadata display	72
5.1.10.	Versioning and delivery format during purchase process	73
5.1.11.	Monetized dataset added to cart.....	74
5.1.12.	Cart checkout	75
5.1.13.	Login prompt when trying to checkout.....	76
5.1.14.	On the fly registration of unregistered user.....	77
5.1.15.	Billing information during checkout process	78
5.1.16.	User comments and order finalization	79
5.1.17.	Order confirmation prompt.....	80
5.1.18.	Representative technological stack	80

6. PILOTS	82
6.1. Pilot Group and Pilot Sites	83
6.2. Pilot Schedule.....	86
7. IMPACT	89
7.1. Dissemination material.....	89
7.2. Digital dissemination.....	89
7.2.1. Project Website.....	91
7.2.2. Social media channels.....	92
7.2.2.1 Twitter	93
7.2.2.2 YouTube	94
7.2.2.3 SlideShare	94
7.2.2.4 LinkedIn	95
7.2.3 Newsletter, Press Releases and Publications	96
7.2.4 Digital marketing campaigns	97
7.3 Top Relationships	97
7.4 Events	97
7.5 Open Access	99
7.6 Foreseen Collaboration	101
7.7 Reporting on established partnerships	103
8. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE PLANS	105
8.1. Conclusion.....	105
8.2. Future Plans	105

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: API Gateway	44
Table 2: FOODAKAI 2.0 API	44
Table 3: AGRIVI 2.0 API	45
Table 4: Pilot Groups and Pilot Sites FOODAKAI 2.0.....	83
Table 5: Pilot Groups and Pilot Sites AGRIVI 2.0.....	84
Table 6: Pilot Groups and Pilot Sites FOODINSPECTOR.	85
Table 7: Pilot Schedule FOODAKAI 2.0.....	86
Table 8: Pilot Schedule AGRIVI 2.0.....	87
Table 9: Pilot Schedule FOODINSPECTOR.	87
Table 10: Major target groups of the digital dissemination tools and channels.....	90
Table 11: Community and partnerships relevance results	103

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Flow in a simple food supply chain.....	13
Figure 2: TheFSM Vision, Mission, Values	15
Figure 3: The development iterative process followed in TheFSM project for the implementation of applications.....	25
Figure 4: The process that is used to transform users' stories to features.....	26
Figure 5: Screen of the find companies functionality	27
Figure 6: Inspector/Auditor dashboard.....	28
Figure 7: Screen of the company dashboard.....	29
Figure 8: Hazards analysis dashboard	30
Figure 9: Predictive analytics for the ingredients of the company to be inspected	31
Figure 10: Invite a company feature.....	32
Figure 11: My company profile page.....	33
Figure 12: The FOODAKAI platform services.....	34
Figure 13: The big data processing workflow.....	35
Figure 14: Add suppliers feature that allows the import of hundreds of suppliers	35
Figure 15: Import mechanism for suppliers and their ingredients.....	36
Figure 16: An evaluation profile page for a supplier.....	37
Figure 17: Supplier risk assessment matrix.....	39
Figure 18: Suppliers' risk weighting feature	39
Figure 19: Add a new factor for the supplier risk estimation risk weighting feature	40
Figure 20: Administrative panel	41
Figure 21: Add user feature.....	42

Figure 22: Manage user feature.....	42
Figure 23: TheFSM platform component deployment.....	46
Figure 24: TheFSM platform infrastructure.....	47
Figure 25: Welcome page.....	51
Figure 26: Login page.....	52
Figure 27: The dashboard.....	53
Figure 28: Roles management.....	53
Figure 29: Users management.....	54
Figure 30: ABAC policies management and authorization.....	55
Figure 31: Advanced policy query builder.....	56
Figure 32: The policy enforcer testing tool.....	57
Figure 33: Dataset upload step 1, metadata input.....	58
Figure 34: Dataset upload step 2, dataset sampling and column filtering.....	59
Figure 35: User edit modal.....	60
Figure 36: User gets feedback on successful edit.....	60
Figure 37: Advanced date picker.....	61
Figure 38: Dataset upload step 3, access policy setup and optional monetization.....	62
Figure 39: Dataset upload step 4, overview summary and final confirmation.....	62
Figure 40: Welcome page.....	64
Figure 41: Dataset providers.....	65
Figure 42: Thematic categories of dataset packages.....	66
Figure 43: Creation of custom data package.....	67
Figure 44: Selection of datasets from categories and providers to form custom package.....	68
Figure 45: Advanced filtered dataset search.....	69
Figure 46: Dataset sampling and purchase.....	70
Figure 47: Ordering a dataset.....	71
Figure 48: Dataset's metadata display.....	72
Figure 49: Versioning and delivery format during purchase process.....	73
Figure 50: Monetized dataset added to cart.....	74
Figure 51: Cart checkout.....	75
Figure 52: Login prompt when trying to checkout (user is not logged in).....	76
Figure 53: On the fly registration of unregistered user during cart checkout.....	77
Figure 54: Billing information during checkout process.....	78
Figure 55: User comments and order finalization.....	79
Figure 56: Order confirmation prompt.....	80
Figure 57: Pilots per country and pilots' leaders.....	82
Figure 58: Pilots' Map.....	83
Figure 59: Counting-dissemination measures.....	90

Figure 60: TheFSM Homepage.....	91
Figure 61: TheFSM hashtags	93
Figure 62: Content of the TheFSM's social media posts.....	93
Figure 63: TheFSM Twitter profile	94
Figure 64: TheFSM YouTube channel	94
Figure 65: TheFSM Slideshare profile	95
Figure 66: TheFSM LinkedIn profile.....	96

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Scope

In early 2020, “The Food Safety Market” project (TheFSM) was granted in the EU H2020 programme (Grant Agreement number: 871703). This project aims to deliver an open industrial virtual data platform that will facilitate the exchange and connection of data between different food safety actors who are interested in sharing information critical to certification. The D8.6 – Published Project Report summarises the achievements and outcomes of the project for the reporting period (M1-M18), targeted to the general public.

1.2. Audience

This report is a public document available to all the members of the consortium and open to the public through the TheFSM website.

1.3. TheFSM Mission, Vision & Values

The vision statement describes where the TheFSM platform wants to be in the future; the mission statement describes what the TheFSM platform needs to do now to achieve the vision. The vision and mission statements must support each other, but the mission statement is more specific. It defines how the platform will be different from other products with similar characteristics in its industry.

TheFSM Mission is to develop a transparent data-powered certification ecosystem for a safe food supply chain.

A **food supply chain** refers to the processes that describe how **food** from a farm ends up on consumers' tables. The processes include production, processing, distribution, consumption and disposal. (Center for Health and the Global Environment of Harvard)

The food is reaching the consumers via food supply chains through which food moves consistently in domino-like motion from producers to consumers whereas the money consumers pay for food goes to various steps of the food supply chain vice versa

Every single stage of the supply chain needs human and/or natural resources.

The two-sided flow which connects farmers and consumers is influenced by these two sets of domino flows (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Flow in a simple food supply chain

For example, a food supply chain featuring pork products might include feed suppliers or veterinarians, a cooperative of farmers, meat packing and fabrication plants, food distributors, marketers, supermarkets and consumers.

TheFSM aims to deliver an industrial data platform that will significantly boost the way that food certification takes place in Europe and globally. The food certification market is a quite traditional but very data intensive business ecosystem and this led us in formulating the following vision statement.

TheFSM Vision is to catalyse the digital evolution of the business ecosystem that the global food certification market involves.

The values statement, also called the code of ethics, differs from both the vision and mission statements. The vision and mission state where the TheFSM project is going (vision) and what it will do to get there (mission). They direct the efforts of people in the project toward common goals. The values statement defines what the consortium believes in and how people in it are expected to behave—with each other, with project actors and with other stakeholders.

TheFSM values statement is: Make data sharing very easy and extremely affordable for the majority of food sector SMEs.

The way that TheFSM is envisaged, as a platform that may talk to users in their own languages and serve their custom, localised needs, will also help very small, small and medium enterprises of the European food sector respond to the digitisation challenge of the food industry. Data platforms should not only target the industry giants that can afford to invest into expensive and specialized technologies. In this way, the project will contribute to increasing the competitiveness & innovation capacity off all small and medium agriculture and food companies in Europe.

1.4. Structure

The structure of the deliverable is as follows:

Section 2: description of business scenarios, business requirements grouped in users' stories and results per business scenario

Section 3: definition and analysis of the adopted agile development process for the development of the three applications and APIs that will be developed in the context of the project

Section 4: description of the backbone infrastructure and technological stack the platform uses so far and presentation of TheFSM Platform v1.0 demonstrator

Section 5: documentation of the access information for the services of TheFSM backbone infrastructure that are utilised for the implementation purposes of TheFSM platform

Section 6: description of pilot groups, pilot sites and pilot schedule

Section 7: documentation of the various dissemination, awareness and outreach activities and results for the respective period

Section 8: conclusions of the report and future plans

Figure 2: TheFSM Vision, Mission, Values

1.5. Relation to Other Deliverables

This deliverable uses the outcomes reported in D1.1 for the user and business requirements as well as the D4.1 and D4.2 that describe the process and outcomes (i) of the agile and interactive development of the TheFSM applications and (ii) of the iteration and testing of all internal and external software systems respectively. TheFSM Data Market mockups are provided from D3.2. The details for the pilot groups, pilot sites and pilot schedule were extracted from D6.1 and D6.2. Finally, the outcomes from D8.4 and D8.3 considering the dissemination, communication synergy activities were incorporated in this report.

2. PROJECT REQUIREMENTS

This section is focused on presenting the identified and validated TheFSM project requirements (i.e., business, legal, technical and data requirements), which will be the basis of the main functionalities of TheFSM platform and applications.

The requirements were initially extracted from five (5) high level inspection and certification **Business Scenarios - BSc** (Chapter 2.1) in the food sector (food safety management and production systems, PDO/PGI and Organic wine certification, Dutch broiler meat case), which represented the core business activities of end users that are considered the ones that would benefit mostly from the platform.

This first extraction of the project requirements and BSc were followed by the identification and validation through Focus Groups of the **User Stories** (Chapter 2.2), by clearing out/merging the "final" end-users (stakeholders / actors) in each scenario according to their role in TheFSM platform, in order reach common **Project Requirements** (Chapter 2.3) for all common end-users (stakeholders / actors). The Focus Groups (FGs) consisted of a mix of stakeholders who come together to provide input on their needs and they were expected to provide useful input to the buildup and architecture of TheFSM solution.

2.1. Business Scenarios

Business Scenario 1: The retailer

For the implementation of the focus groups (FGs) and interviews, a brief presentation was prepared, based on the proposed agenda for this activity. This presentation was adapted in each case to the specific expertise of the focus group.

Participants were invited through email or phone communications, per case, and appointments were set up with members of the Agroknow team.

After a brief introduction to the project and its objectives, the Retailer scenario was presented, each time adapted to the perspective of the participants. The scenario was followed by the presentation of the relevant mock-ups, the FOODAKAI or Food Inspector, in the case of the auditor. Throughout the session, the participants were asked to provide their feedback and comment on all the aspects of the scenario, as well as the mock-ups, at the same time comparing TheFSM proposed approach to their current workflow. The visuals offered by the mock-up helped participants reflect and comment on specific aspects of the proposed design and workflow.

Business Scenario 2: Food Processing

TUV Austria Hellas implemented 2 FGs, because of the different user stories needed to be evaluated by the relevant end-users and because of the different applications to be used by each end-user.

An informative letter was designed in order to give more specific details regarding TheFSM Platform and the project to the participants

For the implementation of the focus groups, a presentation was designed with all the needed information relevant to the goals of the project and the user stories. Prior to that, the focus groups agenda was written with all the subjects that are needed to be answered during the procedure as the 2nd evaluation of the user stories.

Also, all the participants signed the Final Consent Form. Through this form, were asked if they consent to take part in a European project, which aims to provide all the necessary tools for adopting digital innovation in the food safety certification market.

Due to the difficulties because of the pandemic and the forbiddance of physical meetings, the implementation of the focus groups was held with digital platforms such as Microsoft teams and zoom.

Business Scenario 3: Private Food Safety Standards Certification

TUV Austria ROMANIA contacted potential end users. After evaluating if they have the necessary resources to attend the meeting, such as internet connection, short presentations were made by phone, describing the process and to those who showed interest, the consignment form was sent. After receiving the form signed, presentation days were organized according to the client's schedule. After the Zoom meetings, all the feedback and input requested was communicated via emails.

TUV Austria Cyprus met potential clients that would be interested to enrol in the project. The project and its objectives were described to the clients over the phone and a meeting was booked with those who showed interest. During the meeting, TheFSM Project PowerPoint presentation was explained to them as well as the expectation from them to provide input on their business need. Those who decided to participate in the Focus Group signed the Consent Form.

Business Scenario 4: Organic PDO wine certification: the certifier

During the organization of the FGs, meaning the phone contacts and the initial requests of information from participants, it emerged that wine producers and wine companies were not so interested in TheFSM platform due to several issues: 1) PDO wine production is already highly regulated and its traceability is already granted by law and reported on each PDO bottle; 2) wine processing involves practically no other ingredients besides grape that is often produced in the same farm processing it or in farms engaged in long term cooperation with the processors. This leads to very low risk from the supplier's side.

As a consequence, Valorialia decided to broaden the scope of the scenario, including processors of organic products beyond wine. This will allow assessing the interest of other actor types while maintaining the same certifiers and related procedures.

Due to COVID 19, the FG meetings took place online and the organizers decided on smaller groups in order to enhance the degree of interaction and facilitate debate in smaller groups. As a consequence, 4 FG meetings were organized:

- only certifiers (Valoritalia and other Cbs),
- competent authorities (Ministry) + retailers
- organic PD wines together with other organic processors (bakery, processed vegetables and fruits).
- Few producers who could not participate in the meeting but declared their interest were contacted afterwards and their opinion and requests have been included in the FG outcomes.

Business Scenario 5: Dutch food safety authority (NVWA) Inspection / The Dutch broiler meat supply chain.

WFSR organized two FGs. The first FG was with a branch organization representing the main actors (industries) in the poultry sector in the Netherlands. The second FG was with the inspection department of the Dutch food safety authority.

In the first FG, after the introduction round, a presentation was given providing information on TheFSM project participants, objectives, and infrastructure. In addition, the mockups of the applications FOODAKAI and Agrivi were shown.

In the second FG, a similar programme was given as for the 1st FG, except that in this case, mockups were available (and shown) for all three applications (i.e. FOODAKAI, FoodInspector, and Agrivi).

The FGs were organized online using Microsoft teams.

2.2. Business Requirements Grouped in Users Stories

After implementing the first version of the focus groups, the conclusion was that all the BSc (business scenario) are bounded to the same generic scope, as the one of the "inspection and certification in the food supply chain", and due to the bidirectional interactions and interrelation that exist between its main actors, some common BRs have been recorded amongst the different BSC and the different stakeholder within each BSC.

Specifically, four (4) reference BR Categories had been introduced in our BR analysis, under which all the 175 identified BRs were allocated. These four reference BR categories had been adapted based on both the relevant customized international literature for developing business scenarios (Manager's Guide to Business Scenarios, by The Open Group Architecture Forum) and the former experience of the WP1 project team.

These reference BR categories were:

- 1. rBRc 1: Improve business process performance**
- 2. rBRc 2: Improve business operation**
- 3. rBRc 3: Improve management efficacy**
- 4. rBRc 4: Improve business continuity & sustainability**

(rBRc: reference BR category)

From the first implementation of the focus groups, the conclusion was that the most important categories, in terms of the number of the relevant BRs gathered were, **rBRC3** management efficacy and **rBRC4** Business Continuity & Sustainability.

The user stories that consequently developed from the reference categories, are the sum of these business requirements under each one of the four reference categories, which addressed a specific need regardless of the end user that presented in each business scenario. The user stories attempt to answer critical questions raised by each end user, which are “What I want to do” with each BR and “Which will be the outcome” to expect as a tangible result.

For that reason, it was significant to evaluate the user stories theoretically from the perspective of facilitating the food safety certification information exchange in the food supply chain, and validate them with representative companies of this supply chain, aiming to prioritize them as basic components of TheFSM functionalities to be served.

2.3. Requirements' Results

2.3.1. Business requirements

Through the individual assessment (evaluation and validation process) of the “User Stories” based on each one of the five high-end Business Scenarios, we achieved (i) to confirm the adequacy of the identification of the main Business Requirements that address the critical day-to-day needs of the stakeholders in each specific food supply chain and (ii) to prioritize these Business Requirements based on the corresponding needs that each Business Scenario addresses, from the perspective of exchanging necessary info for some basic food safety certification processes.

The results which obtained through the quantitative method used for prioritizing the “User Stories” of the individual Business Scenarios, allow us to come up with a generic prioritization of all the recognized “User Stories”, regardless the Business Scenario. The expected overall results from such an action will reveal the needed sequence to lead the development of the appropriate technical functions (Applications) to be incorporated in TheFSM platform, which respectively will provide the critical solutions to each stakeholder of the supply chain who consequently constitute the main end user of TheFSM platform.

To this end, all the individual final prioritization results of each one of the five Business Scenarios for the User Stories assessed through the combined evaluation and validation process, were assembled.

For those “User Stories” that were assessed (evaluated and validated) in more than one Business Scenarios, their total scoring per BSC was aggregated and an average value estimated per each one of the fifty-one (51) User Stories. Each average value per User Story was classified based on the scoring scale that had been used for the qualitative analysis of the user stories during the validation process.

As a result, each user story categorized against its importance, under the same criteria used for the evaluation and validation of the individual user stories.

The final prioritization of the User Stories, and consequently of the Business Requirements identified and validated through all the Business Scenarios as follows:

High Importance Business Requirements

Based on the quantitative overall evaluation process, twenty-three (23) User Stories were prioritized as of High Importance, that correspond to fifty-three (53) distinct Business Requirements related with the needs of the food supply chain stakeholder.

Medium Importance Business Requirements

Based on the quantitative overall evaluation process, twenty-two (22) User Stories were prioritized as of Medium Importance, that correspond to thirty-three (33) distinct Business Requirements related with the needs of the food supply chain stakeholder.

Low Importance Business Requirements

Based on the quantitative overall evaluation process, six (6) User Stories were prioritized as of Low Importance, that correspond to six (6) distinct Business Requirements related with the needs of the food supply chain stakeholder.

2.3.2. Legal requirements

Processing of Personal Data

In the User Scenarios and on the TheFSM Platform, personal data of natural persons affiliated with business actors are being processed. Such personal data may include contact data, location data, online identifiers and certification data which could be used to identify a natural person.¹

A legal basis for the processing of personal data is established beforehand to ensure the lawfulness of processing. In the context of TheFSM platform and based on the information derived from the Focus Groups, the following legal basis are applicable:

- processing is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract (Article 6 (1)(b)).
- processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject (Article 6(1) (c)). However, please note that obligation to process personal data must be established by statutory law (self-commitment or contractual obligation is not sufficient).
- processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller (Article 6 (1)(e)).

¹ Recital 26, GDPR.

- processing is necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party (Article 6 (1)(f)).

Processing of personal data on TheFSM platform are outlined in the platform's Privacy Policy as documented in D5.2 of Work Package 5.

Governance of Non-Personal Data

In the context of TheFSM, the exchange of non-personal data is governed by contract. This includes data sharing agreements entered into between Actors in each User Scenario as well as the contractual framework governing the use of TheFSM platform.² Establishing data usage and sharing requirements between Actors in each business scenario is an important legal requirement which may be achieved through the review of existing standard contracts and terms of service. Governance of non-personal data on TheFSM platform is being established in the platform's Terms of Use and data sharing agreement, which are developed in Work Package 5, D5.1 and D5.2.

Commercial Exploitation of Databases

In the context of TheFSM public and open data are mainly collected through public authorities and public certification bodies' databases and include laboratories accreditations, approvals and operational licenses. The FOODAKAI application also retrieves information from the databases of public authorities, certification bodies as well as laboratory management systems, CRM/ERP systems and audit systems. Access to these public databases is governed by terms of use and specific licenses.

Based on the Business Scenarios, TheFSM will seek to exploit private databases such as that of GlobalGap. Private databases are protected by a sui generis right of the maker of a database if qualitatively and/or quantitatively a substantial investment in either the obtaining, verification or presentation of the contents was made. In these cases, the maker of a database may prevent extraction and/or re-utilization of the whole or of a substantial part, evaluated qualitatively and/or quantitatively, of the contents of that database.³

Furthermore, there is no Regulatory mandate on private databases to adopt open data policies. Access to private databases is governed by the terms of use and specific license agreements. Therefore, establishing whether there are any restrictions to their intended use constitutes a legal requirement in each business scenario.

UNIVIE has reviewed the Terms of Use of certain private databases, specially GlobalGap. This initial review has indicated that the use of the GlobalGap database is restricted to internal operation of the Customer's organisations only.⁴ Furthermore, there is a general prohibition on making

² See e.g. Guidance on sharing private sector data in the European data economy, SWD/2018/125 final, 6f, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52018SC0125> (12.5.2021) and ICO, Data sharing: a code of practice, <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-sharing-a-code-of-practice/> (12.5.2021).

³ Art 7 Database Directive.

⁴ Sec 8 of Terms and Conditions for the Use of the GLOBALG.A.P. Database, <https://database.globalgap.org/globalgap/TermsAndConditions.faces> (12.5.2021).

information derived from databases publicly available.⁵ Based on these terms, the project faces a challenge in its attempt to integrate data from the GlobalGap database and potentially from other private databases. In light of these obstacles, alternative avenues are investigated by project organizers and responsible technical partners.

Applicable Food Safety Regulations

The Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 sets out an overarching framework for the development of food and food safety legislation and it is complemented by the Regulation (EC) No 852/2004 on the Hygiene of Foodstuffs.

Regarding Pest control, EU Regulation (EU) No 852/2004 requires food business operators to prevent animals and pests from causing contamination by taking the adequate measures.

The following Regulations apply specifically to Business Scenario 4 dealing with Organic Certification. Regulation (EC) No 834/2007, the Organic Regulation sets out the general principles, aims and overarching rules of organic production and organic labelling. EU Organic Certification is required by statute for organic farming, production, distribution, marketing and the use of organic labelling. Regulation (EC) No 510/2006 governs the protection of geographical indications and designations of origin for agricultural products and foodstuffs. This Regulation sets out the broad framework for EU quality standards aimed at protecting the names and unique characteristics of specific products, linked to their geographical origin and traditional know-how.

Food Safety Standards are also applicable and were taken into consideration for each specific Business Scenario. Data sharing requirements and provisions on confidentiality were analysed according to the applicable standards.

2.3.3. Technical requirements

The objective of Technical Requirements is to analyze the current technical landscape of systems and processes being used within the business scenarios from the perspective of connectivity, interoperability, standardization, security and data accessibility.

The main activities of this task focused on mapping the existing technical requirements with the user stories created during the second version, presentation of technical requirements based on v1 of TheFSM platform architecture and partners feedback and finalization of technical requirements in accordance with the respective functionalities of the applications. All the technical requirements have been thoroughly reviewed with technical partners and through the process of mapping with functional requirements, non-functional requirements, business requirements and user stories produced the more detailed second version and mappings with final user stories.

⁵ Sec 2 of Terms and Conditions for the Use of the GLOBALG.A.P. Database.

2.3.4. Data requirements

The main goal of the data requirements is to analyse and document important data flows within each business scenario. The focus is on understanding existing workflows for sharing critical information, either through software systems or through other channels. Then, for each business scenario the corresponding data is also to be documented and analysed - focusing on both primary data sources that are being collected or measured across the supply chain, as well as processed or secondary data that is being generated from the original sources. Representative samples of data have been collected from all partners, to better understand their format, types and sources. Challenges and obstacles are identified in this report in terms of combining different and heterogeneous data sources or transforming data from one format to another.

These requirements will be revisited and updated during the lifetime of the project to ensure that we will capture and meet the data requirements of the business scenarios.

3. APPLICATIONS

The goal of TheFSM is to deliver an open industrial virtual data platform that will facilitate the exchange and connection of data between different food safety actors who are interested in sharing information critical to certification. Extensive piloting will ensure thorough testing of TheFSM's applications and services. Central to this are these applications: FOODAKAI 2.0, AGRIVI 2.0 and FOODINSPECTOR.

Food Inspector

Food inspector is an online dashboard that will primarily serve users from certification bodies. This application will allow inspectors to manage a certification workflow by requesting and accessing data coming from the client who is requesting a new certificate, a renewal or a verification.

FOODAKAI is an intelligent online system that minimizes the food safety risks in the food supply chain by delivering insights about hazards in raw materials and products. It strategically gathers, processes and delivers live food safety data and risk estimation for ingredients, products and suppliers in an easy, fast and cost-effective way.

Agrivi is a farm management software, which enables its user to plan, monitor and analyse all activities on the farm easily. Tillage, planting, spraying, fertilization, irrigation, harvesting and all other activities are managed with a few clicks. Agrivi provides complete support for all crops: fruit, vegetables, grains and other.

3.1. Agile Applications Development Iterative Process

The adopted agile development process includes the following steps

1. **Requirements identification:** Based on the business scenarios a set of user stories were documented and shared with the development team from the partner that leads the development of the application
2. **Design:** Based on the user stories the development team is creating a set of wireframes that gives a good idea of the operations that will be developed. The wireframes are

presented to a focus group of users to validate that the designed operations will bring value to the end users. Based on the feedback we are creating the final version of wireframes

3. **Development:** The final wireframes are used to start the development of the alpha version.
4. **Testing:** the alpha version is tested from the technical and usage point of view by internal teams of technology partners.
5. **Deployment:** Based on the testing results the development team is deploying the alpha version of the application.
6. **Review:** the alpha version is open for testing and review by the focus groups and the feedback is collected using interviews and online questionnaires.

The outcomes of the review are the input for the design and deployment of the beta version. The iterative process is repeated for the beta version and for the first official release of the application (1.0).

Figure 3: The development iterative process followed in TheFSM project for the implementation of applications

The requirements identification step is the sprint 0 and it creates a set of personas and user stories which are added in the sprint backlog. All the stories are organized in Epics (software modules) and the duration of each sprint is from 2-4 weeks. The outcome of each sprint is one or a couple of features that are developed in their alpha version. The end users may be involved in a sprint, if necessary, to provide clarifications about the required functionality of a feature.

Figure 4: The process that is used to transform users' stories to features.

3.2. Outcomes of Agile Development Process

This section reports the developments for the three applications that were implemented in the context of TheFSM, namely

- **Food Inspector** which deploys and validates the software application that inspectors will use in the context of certification scenarios,
- **FOODAKAI 2.0** which further extends and validates the FOODAKAI software application that food companies will use in the context of risk monitoring, traceability and prediction and
- **Agrivi 2.0** which further extends and validates the AGRIVI software application that food processors and their contracted suppliers will use in the context of supplier data sharing scenarios

3.3. Food Inspector Application

This section focuses on the development plan and the outcomes of the agile development process for the Food Inspector application.

3.3.1. Developments status

During the first year of the project, we focused on the design of the features for the Food Inspector application. Below, we present and analyse the wireframes and mockups that were designed and completed within the first year of the project for the Food Inspector application.

Identify companies that need certification services

Using the Food Inspector application, the auditor/inspector will be able to perform an analysis of the market in terms of incidents and inspections being reported. This will help inspector to

- find companies and relevant recalls and inspections
- to find companies with specific criteria e.g., find companies from Greece that produce meat products.

In the following figure, the main screen of the module that can be used to perform the market research is shown.

Figure 5: Screen of the find companies functionality

Auditor Dashboard

The Auditor Dashboard highlights the most important information which the auditor needs to know about the companies which he audits and/or certifies. By clicking on the bar of the expired certificates, the auditor is able to see the list of companies with the expired certificate. When the auditor clicks on the name of a company he will be linked to the next screen.

Figure 6: Inspector/Auditor dashboard

Company profile dashboard

When the auditor clicks on a company name he will be linked to this company dashboard. The main goal of this dashboard is to aggregate all the information that the auditor needs to have to get prepared before the audit. He will be able to see information that is already aggregated for the specific company, but he will be also able to invite the company to submit more information that needs to be shared only with the inspector prior to the audit/inspection.

Figure 7: Screen of the company dashboard

Get prepared for the audit

The food inspector application will provide features that help inspector to perform a risk analysis and prediction for all the raw materials and ingredients that the food company is using and processing. This helps to identify the potential control and critical control points in company's supply chain.

Figure 8: Hazards analysis dashboard

The inspector will be also able to see the predictive analytics for the ingredients of the company and to identify increasing and emerging issues that may affect the safety and quality of company's products.

Figure 9: Predictive analytics for the ingredients of the company to be inspected

Invite company to share all the required information for the inspection

When the inspector will click on the invitation button he will see a pop up window like the one shown in the following screen. The pop up will help him select what type of data the company should share prior to the inspection (audit) and he can send the invitation. An email will be sent to the company with the details of the invitation and a link to enter the system.

Figure 10: Invite a company feature

Data Exchange prior audit/inspection

The food safety and quality assurance experts of the company will receive an invitation to create a profile in the Food Inspector Application.

They should provide information about

- Facilities that they have
- Certificates that they have
- Information about products and ingredients that they are using in the product
- Lab test results and Certificate of Analysis

When the user will click on the Add button a popup window will appear and he will need to add the required data for each category of information.

The shared information will be only available to the Entities (Retailers, Food manufacturers) which are authorized to access the data. Company's expert will be able to select with whom the information should be shared. The shared information will be securely stored in the TheFSM platform.

Figure 11: My company profile page

3.4. FOODAKAI 2.0

This section focuses on the development plan and the outcomes of the agile development process for the FOODAKAI 2.0 application, which will implement the Retailer and Manufacturer business use case scenarios.

3.4.1. Developments status

In this section we present and analyse the developments that have been completed until now for the FOODAKAI 2.0 application.

The FOODAKAI is the food safety intelligence platform that provides risk assessment and predictive analytics services. Within the context of TheFSM project the FOODAKAI application will be extended with functionalities that will allow Retailers and Food Manufactures to perform remote supplier verification.

Figure 12: The FOODAKAI platform services

The data that is used for risk assessment and prediction is collected and processed through a big data platform that focuses on data quality and accuracy. Millions of data records published by National Authorities from all around the world are collected and processed following a methodology that includes several steps as presented in the following diagram.

Figure 13: The big data processing workflow

The new features for FOODAKAI 2.0 that were developed during the first 18 months of the project are presented in the following sections.

Import Suppliers

One of the first features that were developed within the context of the project was the possibility to import all the suppliers that a retailer or food manufacturer has.

Figure 14: Add suppliers feature that allows the import of hundreds of suppliers

To facilitate the process of importing hundreds of suppliers and their ingredients, the development team of Agroknow has designed and implemented a data importing wizard. The

import process includes a step for mapping the properties (columns) of the original file to the GS1 compliant properties of the data model of the TheFSM platform. Values of each property can be also mapped to the ingredient vocabularies used by TheFSM platform.

Figure 15: Import mechanism for suppliers and their ingredients

Supplier evaluation profile

Based on the requirements of Retailers and Manufacturers, Agroknow team developed a food safety evaluation page that aggregates all the critical information for the food safety profile of a company. The user has access to all the historical recalls and border rejections in which the company was involved as well as the outcomes of the inspections that were conducted in this company by the Authorities.

Using the Automated Supplier Risk Assessment module, the user can fully automate the process of analysing the risk for all Retailer's suppliers and performing a risk ranking that will help the user focus on the ones that are susceptible to risks.

The automated supplier risk assessment consists of four (4) steps.

Step 1: User can check the food safety history of your suppliers before starting working with them, using the name of the supplier to find the relevant incidents, inspections, and warning letters.

Step 2: User can add the preferred suppliers to the FOODAKAI and continuously monitors them. Agroknow can help Retailer's users to add hundreds of suppliers to the platform.

Step 3: For all the selected suppliers, FOODAKAI user can create a supplier's risk matrix with a risk score that is estimated using several parameters such as the risk of ingredients that the supplier is using, the risk of his incidents, border rejections, warning letters, and inspections.

Step 4: The supplier's risk matrix is not fixed. The user can adjust the risk assessment score to **the user's approach** by selecting how each parameter will contribute to the overall score.

FOODAKAI supplier risk estimation includes the following parameters

- **Ingredients risk** that is estimated using the Risk Assessment module. This parameter corresponds to the risk of the ingredients that are used by the specific company. The score is the risk that was estimated for the ingredient with the highest risk. Please check how risk is estimated in FOODAKAI (link to risk documentation).
- **Incidents risk:** this is the risk that is estimated based on the frequency and severity of the incidents (recalls and border rejections) that were reported for this company.
- **Recalls:** The number of food recalls that were reported for the specific company and its subsidiaries by National Authorities from all around the world.
- **Border rejections:** The number of border rejections (import refusals) that were reported for this company and its subsidiaries by National Authorities from all around the world.
- **Inspections:** the number of inspections that the supplier had in which an action was indicated.
- **Warning letters:** the warning letters that were announced by the National Authorities for this company.

Risk table for my suppliers 🔍 CHANGE SETTINGS

Search...

Supplier	Incidents Risk	Ingredients Risk	Recalls	Border Rejections	Inspections	Warning Letters	Expired Certificates	Overall Risk Score
Supplier A	2.59	10.01	47	1186	17	3	1	1263.6
Supplier B	2.76	2.64	51	106	19	1	-	181.4
Supplier C	2.14	5.48	26	53	15	2	1	101.63
Supplier D	10.71	3	15	41	18	1	-	84.71
Supplier E	5	2.3	2	23	30	3	-	60
Supplier F	6.6	2.2	17	15	8	1	-	46.6
Supplier G	2	5.48	4	16	18	1	1	45.48
Supplier H	2	2.5	3	5	2	-	-	44
Supplier K	2	3	1	1	1	-	-	15

Figure 17: Supplier risk assessment matrix

The automated risk assessment module includes a feature which allows users to adjust the contribution of each factor to the overall risk score for a supplier.

Risk table for my suppliers 🔍 CHANGE SETTINGS

Search...

Change Supplier Risk Settings

Risk Weights

Incidents Risk ●

Ingredients Risk ●

Recalls ●

Border Rejections ●

Inspections ●

Warning Letters ●

Expired Certificates ●

Supplier	Incidents Risk	Ingredients Risk	Re	Warning Letters	Expired Certificates	Overall Risk Score
Supplier A	2.59	10.01	47	3	1	1263.6
Supplier B	2.76	2.64	51	1	-	181.4
Supplier C	2.14	5.48	26	2	1	101.63
Supplier D	10.71	3	15	1	-	84.71
Supplier E	5	2.3	2	3	-	60
Supplier F	6.6	2.2	17	1	-	46.6
Supplier G	2	5.48	4	1	1	45.48
Supplier H	2	2.5	3	-	-	44
Supplier K	2	3	1	-	-	15

Figure 18: Suppliers' risk weighting feature

Add data a Supplier risk factor

Within the context of TheFSM, we developed a feature that allows the integration of a new parameter for the suppliers risk assessment. This can be done by adding a new column and uploading the data for the suppliers e.g. upload the number of expired certificates.

Figure 19: Add a new factor for the supplier risk estimation risk weighting feature

In addition, the user can download the risk assessment matrix for your suppliers and use it in his internal food safety systems.

3.5. AGRIVI 2.0

The main goal is to further extend and validate the AGRIVI software application that food processors and their contracted suppliers will use in the context of supplier data sharing scenarios.

3.5.1. Developments status

We focused on analyzing and designing the required initial extension of the AGRIVI software that will further extend the flexibility of the software to support the desired data sharing scenarios for different stakeholders in the value chain. The process was followed by the development activities which enabled the software to support the additional actors, other than food processing companies with their contracted farmers, such as consultants and auditors to collaborate with farmers through a farm management software AGRIVI in a digital way.

Development included extending the AGRIVI software with the options to:

- Create new role
- Manage new role permission setup
- Activate or deactivate the newly created role for the adequate food processing and/or farmer AGRIVI account option

- Create newly created user role for the food processing company and/or farmer using AGRIVI with only the desired permission setup and the view option for the desired permission setup

Roles and Permissions Administrative Panel

Roles and permissions administrative panel serves the AGRIVI support staff to create a new role for the software. Through the administrative panel, administrator is enabled to:

- Create a new role
- Name the new role
- Select to which AGRIVI accounts this role should be activated (i.e. specific food processing company and farms)
- Define which user permissions should the new role contain
- Enable/disable the new user role
- Edit/delete the new user role

This administrative panel can only be accessed and managed by AGRIVI staff supporting the project.

Figure 20: Administrative panel

Add User with New Role

This feature enables the end users to create a new user to which the newly created role through the administrative panel will be assigned.

This user will contain only the permissions which were enabled to the new user role to ensure that the new user with access can only see the parts of the software they need to.

This feature is managed by the end user.

Figure 21: Add user feature

Role:	Name:	E-mail:	Phone:	Address:
Owner	Adam Nowak	adam.nowak@agrivi.com	+48 798338776	Warsaw
Manager	Spanish User	spanish.user@agrivi.com		
Administration	Alec Davis	alec.davis@gmail.com		
Analyst	Ann Smith	annsmith@agrivi.com		Warsaw
Consultant	External Consultant	consultant@test.com		
Worker without access	Allen Adams			

Figure 22: Manage user feature

3.6. TheFSM Applications Interface

In this section, we present the information gathered about the interfaces required for the implementation of the integrated platform by defining the communication between the components.

3.6.1 Data Exchange Scenarios

The first version of the integration of TheFSM Applications with TheFSM Platform supports two main data exchange scenarios which were selected based on two main criteria: a) the inclusion of the core technical integration points between the external applications and the platform, and b) the added value for the external applications. The integration of TheFSM Applications with TheFSM Platform is a loosely coupled integration process taking place through the API Gateway. More specifically, each application owner as data provider needs to do the following: a) register the API that is planned to be shared through TheFSM Platform and b) define the access policies that are applied on this API, c) follow the steps for authentication/authorization the provided API might require (via API key or JWT provided by the API Gateway side). Additionally, as a data consumer, the following steps are provisioned: a) search the API that he/she is interested to consume, b) select the API that he/she is interested in, c) follow the steps for authentication/authorization. As soon as these steps are performed, TheFSM Platform acts as a secure proxy between the parties and performs authentication, authorization and secure data sharing. The data exchange scenarios are presented below:

- a. An external application provides data as a data provider through an API. The data provided by the API have access restrictions. The same application needs to share these data with a restricted list of users through TheFSM Platform.
- b. An external application wants to consume data provided through an API from another external application. The shared data are under access restrictions from the data provider.

The next sections document the API interfaces involved in the aforementioned data exchange scenarios, as well as, the relevant integration points as they are supported by the API Gateway. For each API interface we provide the following information:

The following subsections describe these interfaces by detailing the following information:

- **Description:** describes the purpose of the interface.
- **Component providing the interface:** describes the component that is offering the described interface.
- **Consumer components:** describes the components that are using the described interface.
- **Type of interface:** REST, XML-RPC, GUI, Java API etc.
- **Input data:** describes data that is required by the described interface (e.g., Methods or Endpoints, values and parameters of the interface)
- **Output data:** describes the data that is returned by the described interface (e.g., the returned data of methods or REST call)

- **Constraints:** Any other constraints (e.g., specific prerequisites, data-types, encoding, transfer rates) which apply to the interface.
- **Responsibilities:** Partner that is responsible for the implementation and usage of the interface.

3.6.2 API Gateway

Table 1: API Gateway

Name: API Gateway	
Description	Interface of the API Gateway Service
Component providing the interface	API Gateway
Consumer components or External Entities	All integrated services into the platform and/or services wishing to have out of the box support of ABAC protection
Type of Interface	REST
Constraints	N/A
Responsibilities	UBITECH

3.6.3 FOODAKAI 2.0 API

Table 2: FOODAKAI 2.0 API

Name:	
Description	REST API that provides access to all the incidents and supplier data that are used by the FOODAKAI 2.0 application for risk monitoring, risk assessment and risk prediction. Documentation available at http://docs.agroknow.com/ .
Component providing the interface	Food Safety Incidents (FSI) data platform of Agroknow
Consumer components or External Entities	Access to food safety incidents and suppliers data through API
Type of Interface	REST (JSON)
Constraints	Authentication through API Key
Responsibilities	Agroknow is responsible for further development, testing, operation and maintenance of the API

3.6.4 AGRIVI 2.0 API

Table 3: AGRIVI 2.0 API

Name: AGRIVI API	
Description	AGRIVI 2.0 API
Component providing the interface	API
Consumer components or External Entities	Access to farm data through API
Type of Interface	REST (JSON)
Constraints	N/a
Responsibilities	Agrivi is responsible for further development, testing, operation and maintenance of the API

4. THEFSM PLATFORM

4.1. Backbone Infrastructure

Figure 23: TheFSM platform component deployment.

The deployment of the technical solution of TheFSM Platform into production involves the deployment of a single **docker-compose image** (Figure 21) representing the entire platform.

TheFSM deployment (Figure 21) is further divided into conceptual components. **Each conceptual component consists of one or more docker images** for encapsulation, scalability and turning them into microservices, greatly enhancing their utilization. Additionally, the platform communicates with the external third-party applications of Agroknow and Agrivi and other external datasources, also allowing for future integration of developers' APIs, who have expressed interest in processing the offered data of the platform.

Figure 24: TheFSM platform infrastructure

The above figure illustrates the same infrastructure, this time inside the Virtual Machine (VM) the platform is hosted. More specifically:

- The bottom level represents the operating system (CentOS) of the VM.
- The middle level represents the container engine user (Docker's Engine and Daemon).
- The top level represents all dockerized services we currently have successfully deployed and integrated, as well as future dockerized services we will add in the next iterations

During the development of the platform more docker images and conceptual components will be added to the infrastructure diagram. During our internal testing (stress tests included) of the platform's functionality, we did not observe any scalability or performance issues. Nevertheless, we designed the provided services and the database layer to be scalable.

4.2. Technology Stack

TheFSM Platform applies the **containerization paradigm**, as mentioned above. This allows the development of **secure, scalable, isolated applications, enabling the selection among a variety of technologies and tools**, depending on the needs of each microservice. Based on this, the technology stack of each layer and/or each component is provided below:

Access Control and Authentication

4.2.1. Authorization and Access Control Engine:

- Web application backend level:

- Spring Boot⁶: A well-known and industry-standard framework for Java development.
- JCasbin⁷: A well-known and industry-standard library involving ABAC (Attribute Based Access Control). JCasbin is the Java flavour of Casbin, an authorization library that supports access control models like ACL, RBAC, ABAC for Golang, Java, C/C++, Node.js, Javascript, PHP, Python, .NET (C#), Delphi, Rust, Dart/Flutter and Elixir. It is another well-known library used in the industry by companies such as Intel, VMWare, Docker, Orange, Cisco, Microsoft, Verizon, RedHat, IBM and T-Mobile. We opted for JCasbin due to its simple, yet powerful PERM (Policy, Effect, Request, Matchers) meta-model.
- Frontend/UI level:
 - Javascript with jQuery⁸: Enhanced capabilities due to jQuery. Additionally, extra plugins/libraries are used, such as:
 - SweetAlert⁹: Pretty-modal popup for user notification/feedback.
 - Datatables¹⁰: Very powerful and well-known library for data tables management.
 - QueryBuilder¹¹: Extremely flexible query builder for policies creation and management.
 - Steps¹²: Library enabling easy creation of forms with multiple steps.
 - Validation¹³: Powerful form validator. Guarantees no errors in user's input.
 - Papa-parse¹⁴: CSV processing library. Required for column manipulation of datasets.
 - Bootstrap¹⁵: HTML/CSS library for beautiful and responsive UI design.
- Security:
 - Spring Security¹⁶: A module of Spring's library for security. Enforces HTTPS requests and provides data encryption capabilities. Also required for hybrid data encryption (fully documented later on).
 - JSEncrypt, HybridCryptoJS¹⁷: Libraries for RSA and Symmetric encryption for Javascript. Required for hybrid data encryption (fully documented later on).
- Documentation/API:

⁶ <https://spring.io/projects/spring-boot>

⁷ <https://github.com/casbin/jcasbin>

⁸ <https://www.javascript.com/> and <https://jquery.com/>

⁹ <https://sweetalert2.github.io/>

¹⁰ <https://datatables.net/>

¹¹ <https://querybuilder.js.org/>

¹² <http://www.jquery-steps.com/>

¹³ <https://jqueryvalidation.org/>

¹⁴ <https://www.papaparse.com/>

¹⁵ <https://getbootstrap.com/>

¹⁶ <https://spring.io/projects/spring-security>

¹⁷ <https://travistidwell.com/jsencrypt/> and <https://github.com/juhoen/hybrid-crypto-js>

- The provided API and DTOs are thoroughly documented via SpringFox and Swagger UI¹⁸. It is possible to inspect the entire exposed API, the required parameters, the object structure of DTOs, as well as even test requests and simulate user authentication for testing the provided functionality.

User Authentication Mechanism:

- The authentication module has been implemented according to the approach recommended by the W3C Decentralized Identifiers standard¹⁹:
 - Node.js based Express framework
 - Javascript DID resolver libraries
 - OriginTrail Open source Command Executor framework
 - Ethereum Blockchain DID implementation interfaces (ethr and ERC725 methods)
 - Open source Web3.js library for the Ethereum blockchain DID interface

4.2.2. Data Curation and Semantic Enrichment

Data Curation and Semantic Enrichment services are based on the Ontotext Platform and are shipped as a Docker image and can be deployed with Docker compose along with all dependent components and services. For the development of the Data Curation component, SAI's technological stack was used:

- kong: the API gateway.
- semantic-objects²⁰: schema management service.
- graphdb²¹: triple store. GraphDB is an enterprise ready Semantic Graph Database, compliant with W3C Standards. Semantic graph databases (also called RDF triplestores) provide the core infrastructure for solutions where modelling agility, data integration, relationship exploration and cross-enterprise data publishing and consumption are important.
- mongodb²²: document store. MongoDB is a source-available cross-platform document-oriented database program. Classified as a NoSQL database, MongoDB uses JSON-like documents with optional schemas.
- graphiql²³: GraphQL playground. GraphiQL is the reference implementation of this monorepo, GraphQL IDE, an official project under the GraphQL Foundation.

¹⁸ <https://swagger.io/>

¹⁹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/did-core/>

²⁰ <http://platform.ontotext.com/3.2/semantic-objects/semantic-objects.html>

²¹ <https://graphdb.ontotext.com/>

²² <https://www.mongodb.com/>

²³ <https://github.com/graphql/graphiql>

- fusionauth²⁴: out of the box security authentication service, integrating seamlessly.
- fusion-db²⁵: the fusion internal database. FusionDB is a simple and powerful Multi-model database. It allows storage, management and querying of millions of Documents and Key/Value pairs using XQuery.
- fusion-search: the fusion internal search store.
- grafana²⁶: A very popular and well-used dashboard observability tool, metrics and logging operations.
- influxdb²⁷: open-source time series database used for logs. InfluxDB empowers developers to build IoT, analytics and monitoring software. It is purpose-built to handle the massive volumes and countless sources of time-stamped data produced by sensors, applications and infrastructure.
- telegraf²⁸: open source server agent to help collect metrics from stacks, sensors and systems.

At the core of Ontotext Platform is the Semantic Object service. A declaratively configurable service for querying and updating knowledge graphs. Users can write powerful GraphQL queries that uncover deep relationships within the data while not having to be overly concerned about the underlying database query language. Data can be modified and validated against configured data shapes with simplicity and ease. The Semantic Object service transpiles GraphQL queries and mutations into the Platform's different data storage layer query syntaxes. Queries and mutations are invoked, joined and validated, providing a simplified developer experience for those use-cases when GraphQL is sufficient.

4.2.3. Data Market Modelling

For the development of the Supplier & Product Risk Assessment Models, the incident Prediction Models, the risk prediction models and the supplier risk prediction models, the following software stack is used:

- Django framework
- Python 3.9
- elasticsearch
- Keras library
- Prophet Library
- Apache airflow

²⁴ <https://fusionauth.io/>

²⁵ <https://fusiondb.com/>

²⁶ <https://grafana.com/>

²⁷ <https://www.influxdata.com/>

²⁸ <https://www.influxdata.com/time-series-platform/telegraf/>

- Kibana
- Logstash

4.3. TheFSM Platform Prototype

The current section presents **TheFSM Platform v1.0 demonstrator**. The demonstrator covers the **core backend services** regarding: **access control, user authentication and authorization** and **data security at transit and at rest** and **decentralized identity management**, as well as, **the integration with the backend data curation services** provided the main steps of the data asset upload, mapping, policies definition, storage and encryption-decryption. The UI developed for the demonstrator will be updated and replaced with the final UI adopted by TheFSM Platform, developed within the tasks of TheFSM Data Market.

4.3.1. Administrator

User Login

Upon visiting the web platform, the user is welcomed with the following screenshot:

Figure 25: Welcome page.

The user is then prompted to put their username and password in order to successfully login, as shown in the next screenshot.

Figure 26: Login page

From this point on, all subsequent requests need **to attach the JWT the user receives upon the success of the operation**. Obtaining the JWT indicates that the user has been **successfully authenticated** by the authentication service and their **DID claims validated**. Every requests forwards this JWT to the authentication service in order to verify the request's user is authenticated. Additionally, the request is filtered through the **specified ABAC policies** and it passes through if the user's attributes grant them access.

Main Dashboard

Figure 27: The dashboard.

Upon successful authentication and authorization (only the super administrator and moderators can visit this page), the user is redirected to the dashboard as shown in the above screenshot.

4.3.2. Security Layer

Roles management

Figure 28: Roles management.

As with all conceptual entities, roles are displayed in a dynamic table. The user can sort the rows in ascending or descending order, while fuzzy search is also supported to filter rows. Additionally, the user can select how many rows they wish to see before results are paginated. All CRUD operations are supported. The table displays the name of each role, accompanied by a short description of what the role indicates with respect to privileges

Users Management

Figure 29: Users management.

User management is similar to roles management in many ways. However, creating new users is a pipeline involving multiple subcomponents of the platform. More specifically, when creating a new user, the following steps take place under the hood:

- The user is assigned a new DID by the authentication service.
- The list of available roles to assign to the user is provided by ABAC's roles management service.
- The user creation request is filtered through the authentication service and then through ABAC's policies. Since only administrators and moderators can access this API (and the UI), the request is authorized.
- The new user is stored by ABAC's users management service.

The table displays the following fields:

- The user's DID.
- Their username.
- A list of roles they have, separated by commas.

- Enabled status. If a user is disabled, they won't be able to take any action even if they otherwise would. This provides even more fine-grained control over resource access.

Policy Management

Figure 30: ABAC policies management and authorization.

The provided functionality of the policy management is one of the most fundamental parts of the platform in order to ensure fine-grained access to all resources. The table shows all policies used by the super admin and the moderators. More specifically, it shows:

- The actual condition the policy requires to have an effect.
- The resource this policy is applied on.
- The action this policy and resource is applied.
- The effect this policy will have if it matches with a user's attributes. Can be "allow" or "deny", effectively granting or denying them access.
- The active status of the policy. Policies might need to be temporarily disabled (e.g., for maintenance), which is what this field facilitates.

Figure 31: Advanced policy query builder.

The above screenshot illustrates the advanced query builder when adding new policies to the platform. Since the condition(s) which must be met when enforcing policies is critical, building those conditions must avoid error input at all costs. Consequently, all policies are built with the multi-condition builder shown above. The builder supports AND/OR conditions between individual rules, as well as groups, while it also supports negation (NOT). These can be applied at any level of the required condition. Rules or entire groups can be deleted, while it is also possible to drag and drop rules and/or groups, allowing quick, on the fly corrections and minimizing the number of actions a user must do. Each rule also has a small description, explaining to the administrator what the selected filter is trying to accomplish. The depth and complexity of conditions is infinite, allowing any desired effect to be enforced. The builder supports the following fields in condition building:

- Arbitrary access (anyone can access).
- User filtering. Users must belong (respectively, NOT belong) to a set of selected users.
- Role filtering. Users must have (respectively, NOT have) a role from a set of selected roles.
- Year filtering. The year of the request must be (respectively, NOT be) greater than, less than, equal, less or equal than, greater or equal than or between two years.
- Month filtering. The month of the request must belong (respectively, NOT belong) to a set of selected months.
- Day filtering. The day of the request must be (respectively, NOT be) greater than, less than, equal, less or equal than, greater or equal than or between two days.
- Day name filtering. The day of the request must belong (respectively, NOT belong) to a set of selected days. Instead of numerical, this filters day names. It can be useful for example when restricting access to a resource during weekends.

It is worth noting that all filters are validating before submission, preventing moderators and the super admin from making mistakes, while multi-select fields such as users, roles, months and day names are filled by autocomplete/search/tag selection.

Policy Enforcement Testing

Figure 32: The policy enforcer testing tool.

This screenshot shows the policy enforcer testing tool. After setting up new policies or editing existing ones, it is useful for administrators and moderators to have the ability to test their setup with simulated requests, which is what this tool does. The form consists of simulated attributes a user would have (it assumes a user is already authenticated since it is testing the policy enforcement, not the authentication). Additionally, a resource, desired action and date are selected. The request is being tested against the ABAC enforcement engine and a visual status notifies the administrator or moderator about whether the request would go through.

4.3.3. Data Management Layer

Data Asset Management and Policies Definition

The steps presented in the current section will be further developed and refined until the next iteration. It is one of the most complex integration points in terms of interaction flows, as it involves multiple components and services.

The dataset management process consists of four main steps in total, each explained separately. These steps are identified as **prerequisites and are prioritized** to be implemented first regarding the data management process, supported by TheFSM Platform.

The form is dynamic and supports navigation to previous steps until submission, allowing the user to quickly change/correct their input without losing their progress.

The screenshot shows the 'Dataset upload' interface in the 'ABAC Admin' system. The '1. Information' step is active, showing a form with the following fields:

- Dataset name ***: A text input field containing 'Dataset test 1'.
- Tags ***: A text input field with a 'Fetch tags' button next to it.
- Description ***: A text area containing the text 'Sample description for dataset test 1'.

Navigation buttons for 'Previous' and 'Next' are visible at the bottom right of the form.

Figure 33: Dataset upload step 1, metadata input.

The first step of the process, “Dataset Information”, gathers metadata about the dataset about to be uploaded. Such metadata include a dataset name, a small summary and thematic tags (obtained by a backend service). As this pipeline becomes more refined, more metadata will be included.

The screenshot shows the 'Dataset upload' interface in the 'ABAC Admin' system, now at the '2. Structure' step. A 'Choose CSV File' button is visible at the top left. Below it, a table displays dataset records with the following columns:

CONTENT TYPE	TITLE	ABBR	e-ISSN	ARCHIVE URL
Survey	ing Surveys	ACM Comput. Surv.	1557-7341	http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=12048&picked=prox
Journal	of Computer Documentation	ACM J. Comput. Doc.	1557-9441	http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=1248&picked=prox
Journal	on Emerging Technologies in Computing Systems	J. Emerg. Technol. Comput. Syst.	1550-4840	http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=1967&picked=prox
Journal	ita and Information Quality	J. Data and Information Quality	1936-1953	http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=1191&picked=prox
Journal	Journal of Experimental Algorithmics	J. Exp. Algorithmics	1084-6654	http://dl.acm.org/citation.cfm?id=1430&picked=prox

Navigation buttons for 'Previous' and 'Next' are visible at the bottom right of the form.

Figure 34: Dataset upload step 2, dataset sampling and column filtering.

The next step is “Dataset structure”. Here, the user selects a file (ex. .csv) which is their local dataset to be uploaded. The dataset is encrypted with the hybrid encryption approach explained above (Section **Error! Reference source not found.**) and it reaches the platform. This is to ensure their data remain protected. Upon receiving, the platform decrypts the dataset (important note: nothing is stored in the platform’s database so far) and displays it visually as shown above. To avoid clutter and for performance reasons, the first five rows are displayed. At this point, the user can select the columns they wish to keep from the dataset when finalizing the upload process.

4.3.4. Design principles

In this subsection, we provide a few examples illustrating the simplification of the interactions of the user with the application, as well as visual feedback, both aspects being crucial for a good user experience. When developing applications, it is paramount to make a user’s experience as good as possible, as this greatly increases the probability of the user taking an interest in the application. To that end, and taking into consideration **Nielsen’s principles**, we have taken the following into consideration:

- We build a clean interface, avoiding color polluting.
- We build an interface where colors can be correlated to specific actions.
- The user interface is fluid and responsive. It has been tested in smaller devices such as tablets and smartphones, doing our best to display the same content in limited space without subtracting from the overall aesthetics.
- All buttons are accompanied by an indicative icon, offering a quick visual clue to the user, rather than forcing them to read through actions.
- Actions are offered in as few steps as possible.
- We avoid overwhelming the user with options.
- Actions having opposite effects are as distant as possible.
- Similar actions are grouped.
- All forms requiring user input are always validated before submission, preventing the user from making mistakes.
- Wherever possible, autocomplete and tag selection from preselected values is provided to the user.
- Date input is always correct, due to an advanced date picker tool.
- The user is visually notified about the success or failure of their actions. Whenever possible, they also get a description of a potential error status. This is especially important for actions taking time to complete, as the user cannot be sure if the application has stopped working without at least a visual clue.
- Interactions should be as fast as possible.

In TheFSM Platform prototype development the **backend optimizations** and the **Single Page Application design** we opted for (as explained above) ensures a near-native user experience, like the user interacting locally instead of a web app.

Figure 35: User edit modal.

The above screenshot shows an edit modal. It only appears when the user requests this action, keeping the interface clean. All fields are validated before submission and the user is notified about any fields requiring corrections. Additionally, the roles input supports autocomplete, search and tag selection, preventing error input.

Figure 36: User gets feedback on successful edit.

Upon form submission and, provided the operation was successful, the user is notified visually about the operation status, as shown in the screenshot above.

Figure 37: Advanced date picker.

The above screenshot shows the advanced date picker (a reusable UI element in other parts of the platform). Instead of forcing the user to input a date in a specific format and potentially make all sorts of mistakes (order of day, month, year, separator delimiter, 24 hour or 12 hour format etc.), the date picker enabled the user to interact with a calendar and select the exact date they wish. The calendar supports direct year, month and day selection, while also allowing the user to select the exact hour and minute as needed, showing explicitly the 12/24 hour status. While selecting the date, the input date shown in the field is automatically formed (the user is not allowed to manually input anything there). TheFSM Platform will further apply the best practices mentioned previously, to ensure a successful user experience.

Figure 38: Dataset upload step 3, access policy setup and optional monetization.

Next, “Access permissions” follows. This step contains a query builder almost equivalent to the one used in administrators’ policy enforcement (it needs to be adapted to avoid setting up certain conditions that a regular user should never be able to enforce on their own). Roles and users for potential access conditions are obtained from ABAC’s roles and users management services, respectively. After setting up the access permissions condition(s), the user can optionally select to monetize their dataset.

Figure 39: Dataset upload step 4, overview summary and final confirmation.

Finally, step 4 is “Confirm details”. This step provides an overview summary of everything the user has required so far, allowing them to inspect their information with a quick glance and opt to finalize the process. It is important to note that the process can only be finalized **after** the user has checked that they agree with the terms and conditions of the platform (the last checkbox in the above screenshot).

Upon finalization and before being stored, the dataset is forwarded to Data Handler and Data Staging components, which will process the columns of the dataset, mapping them to proper semantic entities from the Semantic Mapper and utilizing the dataset’s metadata to enable analytics on the dataset when the dataset is finally stored. If this operation succeeds, the authentication service will generate a new DID for the dataset.

Three more phases occur under the hood, but are optional. Depending on the dataset tag, the dataset might need to go through the OTN DLT services infrastructure (e.g., when dealing with smart contracts), while the user is prompted to a few more steps, if monetization is involved. Finally, if the dataset is tagged to be an Agroknow or Agrivi dataset, additional steps utilizing Agroknow’s or Agrivi’s services/components might be required (important note: this step is a work in progress as of the moment of writing this report). After all steps are successfully completed, only then is the dataset actually stored in the platform in the Secure Storage.

5. THEFSM DATA MARKET PLACE

5.1. TheFSM Data Market

This section includes the development of low fidelity mockups of TheFSM Data Market. TheFSM Platform prototype, presented in the previous section and TheFSM Data Market will be integrated both aesthetically and technically in the next release of the platform. The provided mockups try to cover as many functionalities as possible. Their scope is to drive the conceptualization of TheFSM platform from the end-user’s perspective. The current mockups will be followed by high fidelity mockups which will guide the development of the platform UIs.

5.1.1. Welcome page

Figure 40: Welcome page.

The above page is the welcome page when the end user visits the marketplace. They are very limited at this point since they are not logged in, but they can still browse dataset categories and create their own data package.

5.1.2. Dataset providers

Figure 41: Dataset providers.

This page shows the data providers, as a quick means to inspect datasets of said provider.

5.1.3. Thematic categories of dataset packages

Figure 42: Thematic categories of dataset packages.

This page displays a shortcut to existing data packages according to predefined categories, additionally offering the option to create a custom data package.

5.1.4. Creation of custom data package

Food Safety Marketplace My Account 0.00€

New Providers Data Packages

Create Your Own Data Package

Food Safety Data > Category > Category

Food Safety Data

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.

Food Alerts

Europe

USA

Asia

Middle East

Scientific Data

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.

Food Recalls

Outbreak Reports

Data Package PREMIUM

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do

Data Package PREMIUM

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do

Search Feedback

Did you find what you were looking for?

If you need help, [contact us](#)

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Figure 43: Creation of custom data package.

This page displays user input while setting up a custom data package. Options include data type (food safety or scientific data), subtype (alerts, recalls, reports) and source area (Europe, USA, Asia, Middle East) etc. All this information serves as metadata also.

5.1.5. Selection of datasets from categories and providers

Figure 44: Selection of datasets from categories and providers to form custom package.

This page displays selection of datasets from various categories and data providers in order to form a custom package.

5.1.6. Advanced filtered dataset search

Figure 45: Advanced filtered dataset search.

This page displays potential filters used in advanced dataset search. The filters include parameters such as categories, delivery type, dataset type, provider, size and upload year.

5.1.7. Dataset sampling and purchase

Figure 46: Dataset sampling and purchase.

This page displays the dataset sampling capabilities before purchasing a premium dataset. Sampling is important, since it allows the end user to inspect a sample of the dataset before purchase, compared to making blind (and potentially risky) purchases.

5.1.8. Ordering a dataset

Figure 47: Ordering a dataset.

This page illustrates the ordering of sample data, if the dataset is not yet available.

5.1.9. Dataset's metadata display

Food Safety Marketplace My Account 0.00€

New Providers Data Packages

Data Package

Price Calculator

Details Documentation

Section 1	Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut enim ad
Section 2	minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex
Section 3	ea commodo consequat.

Duis aute irure dolor in reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident, sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum.

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Figure 48: Dataset's metadata display.

This page displays the dataset's metadata.

5.1.10. Versioning and delivery format during purchase process

Figure 49: Versioning and delivery format during purchase process.

This page displays versioning options and delivery format during the purchase process.

5.1.11. Monetized dataset added to cart

Figure 50: Monetized dataset added to cart.

This page displays visual feedback when adding a dataset to the cart.

5.1.12. Cart checkout

Food Safety Marketplace

 My Account
 XX.XX€

X

[New](#)
[Providers](#)
[Data Packages](#)

Your Cart - 3 Items

	Records	Format	Price	
	Data Package <small>Package Id: XXXXX</small>	123.800 XML	100,00€	Remove
	Data Package <small>Package Id: XXXXX</small>	10.000 CSV	150,00€	Remove
	Data Package <small>Package Id: XXXXX</small>	50.000 XML	1500,00€	Remove
<input type="button" value="Continue Browsing"/>			Total	1750,00€
				<input type="button" value="Check Out"/>

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Figure 51: Cart checkout.

This page displays the cart checkout.

5.1.13. Login prompt when trying to checkout

The screenshot shows the 'Food Safety Marketplace' website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the site name, a 'My Account' link with a user icon, and a shopping cart icon showing 'XXX€'. Below this is a large, faded banner area. Underneath the banner, there are links for 'New', 'Providers', and 'Data Packages'. The main content area features a message: 'To proceed with the check out you must first provide your credentials'. Below this message is a login form with two tabs: 'Log in' (selected) and 'New to Data Shop'. The form contains fields for 'Username' and 'Password', a 'Forgot your Password?' link, and a 'Log in' button. Below the form is a '← Back to Cart' button. At the bottom of the form area, there is a note: 'Note: Instructions for downloading your data package or registering to the API will be sent via email after the completion of the order and the confirmation of the payment'. The footer contains links for 'The Company', 'Terms of Use', and 'Contact', along with the year '2021 ©'.

Figure 52: Login prompt when trying to checkout (user is not logged in).

This page displays the login prompt shown when user tries to checkout, but they are not yet logged in to the platform.

5.1.14. On the fly registration of unregistered user

The screenshot shows the 'Food Safety Marketplace' checkout page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Food Safety Marketplace' on the left, 'My Account' with a user icon, and a shopping cart icon with 'XX.XX€'. Below the navigation bar is a large, faded 'X' watermark. A secondary navigation bar contains 'New', 'Providers', and 'Data Packages'. The main content area features a message: 'To proceed with the check out you must first provide your credentials'. Below this message are two tabs: 'Log in' (selected) and 'New to Data Shop'. The 'New to Data Shop' tab is active, displaying a registration form with the following fields: 'Username', 'Email', 'Password', and 'Repeat Password'. A 'Register' button is positioned below the 'Repeat Password' field. A 'Back to Cart' button with a left-pointing arrow is located below the registration form. At the bottom of the main content area, a note reads: 'Note: Instructions for downloading your data package or registering to the API will be sent via email after the completion of the order and the confirmation of the payment'. The footer contains links for 'The Company', 'Terms of Use', and 'Contact', along with the copyright notice '2021 ©'.

Figure 53: On the fly registration of unregistered user during cart checkout.

This page displays the option to immediately register a new user during the checkout process, if they are not already logged in.

5.1.15. Billing information during checkout process

The screenshot displays the checkout process on the Food Safety Marketplace website. The page header includes the site name and navigation links. The main content area is divided into three columns: 'Your Cart', 'Billing Invoice', and 'Delivery Method'. The 'Your Cart' column lists three data packages with their respective prices and a total of 1750,00€. The 'Billing Invoice' column contains input fields for company name, street address, ZIP/postal code, state/province, city, and country. The 'Delivery Method' column offers options for sending download instructions and a 'Proceed to Payment' button. The footer contains company information and the year 2021.

Food Safety Marketplace My Account XX.XX€

[New](#) [Providers](#) [Data Packages](#)

Your Cart	Billing Invoice	Delivery Method
<p>Data Package Package Id: XXXXX Records: 123800 Format: XML 100,00€</p> <p>Data Package Package Id: XXXXX Records: 123800 Format: CSV 150,00€</p> <p>Data Package Package Id: XXXXX Records: 123800 Format: CSV 1500,00€</p> <p>Total 1750,00€</p>	<p>Company Name <input type="text"/></p> <p>Street Address <input type="text"/> No <input type="text"/></p> <p>ZIP/ Postal Code <input type="text"/></p> <p>State/ Province <input type="text"/></p> <p>City <input type="text"/></p> <p>Country <input type="text"/></p> <p>Select Country <input type="text"/></p>	<p>Send Download Instructions to</p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> My Registered Email</p> <p><input type="radio"/> other Email</p> <p>Proceed to Payment</p>

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Figure 54: Billing information during checkout process.

This page displays the billing information input during the checkout process.

5.1.16. User comments and order finalization

Food Safety Marketplace My Account XX.XX€

New Providers Data Packages

[Back](#)

Your Cart

<input type="checkbox"/>	Data Package Package Id: XXXXX Records: 123800 Format: XML 100,00€
<input type="checkbox"/>	Data Package Package Id: XXXXX Records: 123800 Format: CSV 150,00€
<input type="checkbox"/>	Data Package Package Id: XXXXX Records: 123800 Format: CSV 1500,00€
Total 1750,00€	

Payment Method

Payment in Advance

Bank Name: XXXXXXXXXXXX
Account Holder: XXXXXXXXXXXX
IBAN: XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX
SWIFT: XXXXX
Country: XXXXXXXXX

Once deposited, kindly email us the copy of the bank account transaction to our Sales Department at sales@datashop.com

Please notice that detailed download instructions will be emailed once the deposit is confirmed.

I agree with the [terms of use](#)

Complete Order

The Company Terms of Use Contact

2021

Figure 55: User comments and order finalization.

This page displays the order finalization, while also forcing the user to agree to terms of use and provide any additional comments they wish to add.

5.1.17. Order confirmation prompt

Figure 56: Order confirmation prompt.

This page displays visual feedback, notifying the user that their order has been granted a tracking ID and has been successfully completed.

5.1.18. Representative technological stack

The following is a representative list of technologies which we aim to select for the development of the Data Marketplace:

- **Node JS** for the development of the web API that will be used by the front end
- **elasticsearch** for indexing the information of the datasets that will be published in the Food Safety Market

- **JavaScript** for the development of the front end functionalities
- **Php** for the development of the front end functionalities
- **Wordpress** for the generic content management

6. PILOTS

In The Food Safety Market” (TheFSM) project an extensive piloting is foreseen to test the applications and services developed by the project partners that will be supported and channeled through the infrastructure of the TheFSM. Pilots are foreseen in ten countries during the project duration (i.e. Greece, Netherlands, Italy, Romania, Croatia, Hungary, Poland, Cyprus, Egypt, Jordan) and to ensure optimal pilot execution and product development, a guidance for the participants is essential.

Figure 57: Pilots per country and pilots’ leaders.

Such guidance documents are already prepared entailing a methodology that focuses on specifying the business settings and evaluating scenarios that will be implemented in all countries where pilots will be run.

The process is iterative, agile and lightweight and specifies for each pilot the new workflows that will be taking place, the local business partners to be involved and how they will be involved, as well as the methodological guidelines and necessary materials (questionnaires, etc.) that the involved partners will use.

Figure 58: Pilots' Map

6.1. Pilot Group and Pilot Sites

For a pilot, the candidates were selected after having several meetings with partners that indicated an interest in the TheFSM technology. The selection of a pilot site or sites often depends on the type and location of the pilot participants who have been selected and the number of support staff available to help them.

The number of pilot sites and the size of the pilot users groups were defined based on: i) the objectives of the pilot, ii) the countries where we have partners and support staff, iii) specific technology requirements that can be piloted only by using particular sites or user groups.

The following three table below show the specific information related to FOODAKAI 2.0, Agrivi 2.0 and Food Inspector with regards to the pilot group.

Table 4: Pilot Groups and Pilot Sites FOODAKAI 2.0.

Pilot	Country	TheFSM Resp	Group
P1	Greece	TÜV AU HELLAS	Actors in the food supply chain

P2	Netherlands	WFSR	Actors in the food supply chain
P3	Italy	Valoritalia	Wine producers (all chain)
P4	Romania	TÜV AU Romania	Food processors
P8	Cyprus	TÜV AU HELLAS - TÜV AU CYPRUS	Actors in the food supply chain
P9	Egypt	TÜV AU HELLAS – TÜV AU EGYPT	Actors in the food supply chain
P10	Jordan	TÜV AU HELLAS – TÜV AU JORDAN	All actors in food supply chain

Table 5: Pilot Groups and Pilot Sites AGRIVI 2.0.

Pilot	Country	TheFSM Resp	Applications	Group
P1	Greece	TÜV AU HELLAS	AGRIVI 2.0	Actors in the food supply chain
P2	Netherlands	WFSR	AGRIVI 2.0	Actors in the food supply chain
P3	Italy	Valoritalia	AGRIVI 2.0	Wine producers (all chain)
P4	Romania	TÜV AU Romania	AGRIVI 2.0	Food processors

P5	Croatia	AGRIVI	AGRIVI 2.0	Food processing company farmers
P6	Hungary	AGRIVI	AGRIVI 2.0	Food processing company farmers
P7	Poland	AGRIVI	AGRIVI 2.0	Food processing company farmers
P8	Cyprus	TÜV AU HELLAS - TÜV AU CYPRUS	AGRIVI 2.0	Actors in the food supply chain
P9	Egypt	TÜV AU HELLAS – TÜV AU EGYPT	AGRIVI 2.0	Actors in the food supply chain
P10	Jordan	TÜV AU HELLAS – TÜV AU JORDAN	AGRIVI 2.0	All actors in food supply chain

Table 6: Pilot Groups and Pilot Sites FOODINSPECTOR.

Pilot	Country	TheFSM Resp	Applications	Group
P1	Greece	TÜV AU HELLAS	FOODINSPECTOR	Actors in the food supply chain
P2	Netherlands	WFSR	FOODINSPECTOR	Actors in the food supply chain
P3	Italy	Valoritalia	FOODINSPECTOR	Wine producers (all chain)
P4	Romania	TÜV AU Romania	FOODINSPECTOR	Food processors

P8	Cyprus	TÜV AU HELLAS - TÜV AU CYPRUS	FOODINSPECTOR	Actors in the food supply chain
P9	Egypt	TÜV AU HELLAS – TÜV AU EGYPT	FOODINSPECTOR	Actors in the food supply chain
P10	Jordan	TÜV AU HELLAS – TÜV AU JORDAN	FOODINSPECTOR	All actors in food supply chain

6.2. Pilot Schedule

One of the earliest activities in planning a pilot is to draft a schedule, which is usually included in the master project schedule. The first iteration of the pilots will be in the end of 2021 Q4. Each pilot leader will define the exact date with the partners involved in his pilot. The following three tables below show the scheduled related to FOODAKAI 2.0, Agrivi 2.0 and Food Inspector applications.

Table 7: Pilot Schedule FOODAKAI 2.0.

Pilot country	TheFSM Resp	Estimated period for the first pilot iteration	Estimated period for the second pilot iteration	Estimated period for the third pilot iteration
Greece	TÜV AU HELLAS	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022
Netherlands	WFSR	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022
Italy	Valoritalia	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022
Romania	TÜV AU Romania	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022
Cyprus	TÜV AU HELLAS - TÜV AU CYPRUS	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022

Egypt	TÜV AU HELLAS – TÜV AU EGYPT	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022
Jordan	TÜV AU HELLAS – TÜV AU JORDAN	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022

Table 8: Pilot Schedule AGRIVI 2.0.

Pilot country	TheFSM Resp	Estimated period for the first pilot iteration	Estimated period for the second pilot iteration	Estimated period for the last pilot iteration
Greece	TÜV AU HELLAS	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022
Netherlands	WFSR	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022
Italy	Valoritalia	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022
Romania	TÜV AU Romania	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022
Cyprus	TÜV AU HELLAS - TÜV AU CYPRUS	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022
Egypt	TÜV AU HELLAS – TÜV AU EGYPT	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022
Jordan	TÜV AU HELLAS – TÜV AU JORDAN	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022

Table 9: Pilot Schedule FOODINSPECTOR.

Pilot Country	TheFSM Resp	Estimated	Estimated	Estimated
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		period for the first pilot iteration	period for the second pilot iteration	period for the last pilot iteration
Greece	TÜV AU HELLAS	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022
Netherlands	WFSR	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022
Italy	Valoritalia	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022
Romania	TÜV AU Romania	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022
Cyprus	TÜV AU HELLAS - TÜV AU CYPRUS	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022
Egypt	TÜV AU HELLAS – TÜV AU EGYPT	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022
Jordan	TÜV AU HELLAS – TÜV AU JORDAN	Q4, 2021	Q2, 2022	Q4, 2022

7. IMPACT

7.1. Dissemination material

TheFSM dissemination team deploys an inbound communication strategy, enhanced with a wide variety of communication material that will be shared with stakeholders. The dissemination team will create and produce a set of promotional materials (i.e., banners and brochures) that will be used for dissemination purposes. The initial steps of the communication strategy were the development of the project's logo, motto line, social media icons and social media headers and banners, and all assets needed to communicate the messages of the project. Additionally, a presentation template and a document deliverable template were created in order to ensure visual coherence among the presentations that will be held from each project partner. Especially for the selection of the project branding, a collaborative approach was followed right after the online kick-off of TheFSM. An online poll was set up (<https://forms.gle/pQEZcTsdTVinAtfB6>), including the four different options that were prepared by Agroknow designers. All partners voted for the existing logo – and included comments that were adapted in the final logo version (also visible on the top left side of the heading of this deliverable). All additional options, and the voting page can be found on the Annex A.

Which logo do you vote for TheFSM ? *

Option 1

Option 2

Option 3

Option 4

All the above-mentioned digital assets are available for each partner of the consortium in the Google drive folder of TheFSM project. During the project's lifetime, additional material, such as promotional videos and success stories, will be produced to capture the attention of the audience and demonstrate the impact of the project. In fact, for every pilot, video interviews of the actors involved (e.g., food scientists, food safety professionals, certification consultants, SMEs) will be produced in order to highlight the key achievements and advancements of the project.

7.2. Digital dissemination

This section provides the list of the project's online dissemination channels that are used to promote its main outcomes and to attract the targeted stakeholders to actively participate in its activities. The main online dissemination mean is the project's website that presents all the related information and the progress made so far. Additionally, social media are the key online channels for informing the target groups about the project's outcomes and the dissemination activities, like the presentation in key events (workshops and conferences) and the organization of the project's workshops. Besides disseminating project's results among the research community, policy-makers, and the private and public sector, TheFSM makes a particular effort towards communicating the project's information to a wider audience:

Digital dissemination tools and channels	Main Target Groups					
	Certification bodies	Certification scheme owners	Food distributors & retailers	Primary producers & farmers	ICT contributors to TheFSM technology stack	Providers of ICT services to the food sector
Website	√	√	√	√	√	√
Social Networks	√	√	√	√	√	√
Videos	√	√	√	√		
Press releases	√	√			√	√
Publications	√	√			√	√
Newsletter	√	√	√	√	√	√

Table 10: Major target groups of the digital dissemination tools and channels

Moreover, TheFSM consortium utilizes all the existing dissemination tools which suit the most both to the consortium interest and to the dissemination strategy, exploiting all the provided opportunities to achieve greater impact and visibility. To measure our effectiveness and to guarantee wide expansion of the project’s outcomes during its lifetime, we set some internal indicators per channel, as it is depicted on the following figure:

Figure 59: Counting-dissemination measures

7.2.1. Project Website

The project's website (www.foodsafetymarket.eu) is the main online communication channel used to promote the project and increase the stakeholders' awareness regarding its activities. The appearance of the website is coherent with the brand and the general communication strategy and the central management of the website is undertaken by Agroknow. TheFSM website provides general information about the project's vision, objectives, progress and important results, workshops and other related events of the project. Also, it follows a responsive design approach to be user-friendly on all types of devices (desktops, laptops, tablets and mobile phones). Social media buttons are available on the bottom part of the website to facilitate access to our social media channels and to capture stakeholders' interest, get them to follow, like and share our content.

Furthermore, the website establishes connection to offline dissemination activities promoting them and providing scientific papers and official deliverables for download. Also, on the website a visitor can find direct links to our consortium partners websites, by clicking on their logos. Additionally, team member interviews will be carried out and published on the website.

Figure 60: TheFSM Homepage

The project's website was launched in May 2020 (M4). Its main pages are: Home, About, News & Events, Pilots, Results, Contact. Moreover, the website's activity is monitored through Google Analytics in order to gather information about the website's traffic and how visitors interact within it. Finally, in order to assure a good visibility in search engines (such as Google), on page and off page SEO actions will be undertaken and periodically updates of the website will be carried out.

7.2.2. Social media channels

Social networks are used to inform and stay connected with the professionals, policy makers, scientific community, general public, and other stakeholders. Agroknow is responsible for all of the social media activities and for the creation of relevant content, sharing the news, posting on social media and monitoring outreach. Apart from the official social media channels, the project needs the support and active involvement of all project partners through their organizational social media accounts. In order to increase the visibility and outreach of the project and its outcomes, it is suggested for partners to share and publish content from TheFSM's social media accounts and TheFSM's website. This action results in increasing traffic to all project-related work and also generates traction in the websites and social media of the consortium members.

Additionally, for interactive communication purposes, four (4) media channels were designed and publicized in order to expand the outreach of TheFSM throughout and beyond the project's lifespan. The social media accounts of the project which have been created are: a Twitter channel for promoting the material such as success stories and interviews produced within the project, a SlideShare account for uploading the presentations that are held with the project's support, a LinkedIn account to connect with professionals on the topics of the project, a YouTube account for providing the recordings of the project's webinars and other promotional videos that are used to disseminate the technical outcomes of TheFSM.

The selection of the aforementioned social media channels was based on two basic factors:

1. The most cost-effective set of channels for sharing immediate updates from the project to all stakeholders' groups; and
2. The most adequate, valid and powerful media channels for spreading and influencing with novel practices, a wide spectrum and number of key-stakeholders.

Following the selection of the most appropriate social networks, there were several parameters that have been taken into account when creating social media content:

- Interactivity is the main pillar of the generated content as it is the best way to reach the audience and engage with it. Posts focus on the interaction with the online audience while the language is easily understood by non-specialists.
- Eye-catching posts lead to higher conversions with prioritization into visuals and graphics that make the piece unique.
- Adaptability of the social media assets to the format and functionality of the several devices. The asset must be used in such a frame to maximize their placement, especially taking into consideration the placement on mobile devices.
- Using relevant content and to the project's outcomes, hashtags help our consortium to reach out the target audience and likewise to make it easier for others to find TheFSM generated and novel knowledge. Towards this, hashtags will segregate the project key topics and increase visibility in the social media environment, while they make our messages stand out and influence the relevant communities. Further tracking of the

hashtags help our consortium to analyse quantitative and qualitative data. The project has set an official distinctive hashtag (#TheFSM) which is used to monitor the posts related to the project. The agreed to be used by the consortium hashtags in TheFSM communication are as follows:

Figure 61: TheFSM hashtags

Additionally, to effectively share information on social media our consortium needs to design posts based on how the audience consumes the message. The following figure explains the steps what a visually appropriate social media post should contain:

Figure 62: Content of the TheFSM’s social media posts

7.2.2.1 Twitter

TheFSM’s Twitter account (<https://twitter.com/theFSMEU>) was created in April 2020 (M3) and proved to be extremely useful so as to inform and engage with our target audiences and their respective communities. Building a community/being part of an already existing community is crucial for dissemination via Social Media platforms. Information about the latest updates on the website, new events, discussions and relevant news will be provided via Twitter. During the lifetime of the project, the goal for the Twitter account traction is to have at least 500 followers and 500 tweets. Through our channel it will be easy for followers to engage with the project, either by following, mentioning, retweeting or commenting on our tweets.

Figure 63: TheFSM Twitter profile

7.2.2.2 YouTube

TheFSM YouTube account (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCEfGNclCEAurc3i2MLLxu7g/>) was created in May 2020 (M4). YouTube is highly regarded as a very effective dissemination channel for video content. More specifically, at this media channel, stakeholders will have the chance to view recordings of the project’s webinars and other project promotional videos, along with content uploaded from partners and videos of the events that will take place. According to the project’s KPIs, on this channel there are going to be published at least 10 videos, including webinars, targeting food safety experts (throughout the project’s duration).

Figure 64: TheFSM YouTube channel

7.2.2.3 SlideShare

The SlideShare account of **TheFSM** was created in April 2020 (<https://www.slideshare.net/TheFSMTheFSM>). At this media channel, stakeholders have the

chance to check all presentations delivered from **TheFSM** partners introducing the project and its outcomes, giving the viewer not only a deep insight into the project but also extra individual aspects. Such presentations can be delivered during public appearances, like conferences, workshops, meetups, webinars, networking sessions and trade fairs. Throughout the duration of the project, this channel should include at least 50 presentations.

Figure 65: TheFSM Slideshare profile

7.2.2.4 LinkedIn

A showcase page was created on LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/theefsmeu>) and the goal was to share updates on a weekly basis with relevant content. This content would be either originally generated by the project's partners or would be content worth resharing from key influencers and opinion leaders of the food safety, food quality, certification, big data and blockchain sectors. LinkedIn is a professional network through which **TheFSM** will take advantage and address specific target groups creating a sustainable network around our project in which both the status and the outcomes of the project could be shared.

Figure 66: TheFSM LinkedIn profile

7.2.3 Newsletter, Press Releases and Publications

One of the project's key communication mediums that is used for communication purposes is the regular newsletter within the target groups and stakeholders of **TheFSM**. The project uses this channel to run campaigns aiming to a variety of food supply chain stakeholders, technological and data providers. It is highly recommended to the project's partners to communicate its objectives and proceedings through their organizational newsletter or mailing lists. The periodic **TheFSM's** newsletter provide a digest of the project's progress and related events, as well as upcoming activities. What is more, the newsletter is distributed by e-mail to the consortium partner's organisations and other parties who have subscribed to it, and our consortium members have the responsibility of circulating it amongst their contacts.

Moreover, in order to increase the outreach to the general public and media, **TheFSM** is sharing publicly two press releases per year on project's stories and outcomes. Aiming to capture the interest of the communities that are active in the consortium countries, it takes into consideration the coverage of the different languages of the project's partners (i.e., Greek, Dutch, Italian, Romanian, Croatian, Hungarian, Polish and Arabic). For selected scientific communities that belong in the project's target groups, the goal is to publish (during Y2&3) at least five (>5) publications to sector-specific (computer science, food safety, etc.) journals or conferences that will be edited by the project's partners and other contributors pertaining the project and the outcomes of the different use cases. Finally, it is expected from all partners to provide a number of news items and blog posts during the project's lifetime. Particularly, 30 high level promotional items and posts will be generated and distributed in the three years of the project's lifetime. All these news items and blog posts will be published and disseminated through the project's social media channels.

7.2.4 Digital marketing campaigns

In this section all the digital marketing campaigns that will be organized during the project's lifetime will be demonstrated. The main aim of the excessive campaigns, which are implemented via the communication and dissemination channels (i.e., social media, blog articles, electronic communication lists, etc.), is to drive engagement, conversions and traffic to **TheFSM**. Moreover, several opinion blog articles containing relevant keywords will be posted on the website in order to boost search engine optimisation (SEO) and achieve showcase of the website in the top search lists of search engine results for relevant queries. The core thematic areas of the campaigns regard food safety and food certification. The number of the recipients of each campaign, the unique opens of each campaign as well as the unique clicks show the impact these campaigns have on the stakeholders.

7.3 Top Relationships

As mentioned in the rationale behind the dissemination strategy of **TheFSM**, the goal is to select and record all top contacts, within the targeted stakeholders' segments, that will help the consortium increase the impact of the project. The different segments spread across the food safety and certification sector including food-safety professionals, food industry representatives, technology partners, key influencers and opinion leaders, policy makers, food authorities and others.

The first step that were realized was to record the main groups of stakeholders, in close collaboration with other WPs and then filter and select according to the project's priorities the relationships that should be nurtured further.

7.4 Events

The participation and organization of events, webinars and workshops is one of the main dissemination tools for – on the one hand – effectively communicating project-related information and findings to the wider European research and scientific community (including also more specialized **TheFSM** target groups, depending on the nature of each event), as well as – on the other hand – for collecting feedback/input by relevant key stakeholders and experts, attending these events. Further these events will provide the possibility of both networking with other groups who work in similar fields at both European and international level and partnering with other related EU-funded projects.

7.4.1 External events

A number of national and international conferences, congresses, workshops, exhibitions and fairs serve as effective dissemination action concerning the discussion and the presentation **TheFSM** achievements, progress and results with other members of the scientific community, directly and indirectly involved in the project. Accordingly, through the 3 years' duration of **TheFSM**, the

participation of the project in several events will provide to our consortium the chance to expand its network and promote **TheFSM** initiative, through either oral presentations, booths and/or stands. To enlarge even more the visibility for our brand and boost the connection with stakeholders and other European projects, partners are encouraged to participate in a high number of events relevant to the project. The aim of the participation in the external events is to:

- Disseminate the **TheFSM** results and novel knowledge;
- Expand and reinforce the stakeholders' network and connect to additional ones;
- Guarantee the impact by promoting **TheFSM** objectives and generated opportunities;
- Collect feedback regarding the dissemination actions and the newly born outcomes.

The announcements of the upcoming external events as well as detailed information for the attendance of our consortium will be announced on our website (under the dedicated section of "News and Events") and social media followed by visuals and pictures from our participation. Finally, it is planned that for some key events organized by the European Commission and other important agents of the sector, the partners will promote joint presentations of the project. Such examples are the following:

1. Participation of **TheFSM** sponsorship, participation & booths in major food industry fairs and exhibitions such as the GFSI Conference, SQF, the GMA Science Summit, World AgriTech and others;
2. Representation to specialised forums, standardisation groups and global networks (e.g., BDVA, GFSI) with the participation of special interest groups.

7.4.2 *TheFSM* events

Apart from participating in conferences, forums and fairs, the consortium, after reaching the visibility of **TheFSM** project among special interest groups, move towards organizing special sessions or workshops per pilot in the context of highly visible conferences that are held on an annual basis. An analysis will be performed in order to ensure that **TheFSM's** sessions and workshops will be tied in with the industry events which have the highest outreach around Europe and globally. The foreseen activities that are linked to events' organization throughout the project's lifetime can be found in the following list:

1. Organization of presentations about **TheFSM** with internal scientific and/or food safety directors.
2. Organization of series of webinars (2 per year) for food safety experts, promoted through project website and other channels.
3. Organization of exchange meetings and joint workshops with future clients.
4. Organization of open days (1 open day per pilot country) inviting anyone interested to find out about **TheFSM** platform and try the produced tools/services.

7.5 Open Access

In terms of expanding **TheFSM's** outcomes and influence a diverse group, spanning numerous scientific sectors and research or application area, our consortium partners agreed on disseminating the project's deliverables, only the public ones, on the EU funded, free-to-use **Zenodo** repository, a central research repository.

Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) is a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) provider that was developed, in particular, to make science more open. It has been funded by OpenAire (<https://www.openaire.eu/>), which is an EU funded project and has therefore been tailored with Horizon2020 projects in mind. Zenodo provides a unique DOI for each deliverable, ensuring its valid and safe disposal. In addition, this facility will make the search process easier, for end users, and therefore increase the deliverables' openness. For this reason, Zenodo was a good fit for the Open Access requirements of **TheFSM** so a community can be created in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/thefsm>). Besides the purpose of being a place to host our deliverables, our consortium is investigating the possibility to upload future large datasets related to research, papers or/and publications with scientific content.

TheFSM partners, understanding the importance of the Open Access and the positive effect and impact that this movement can have, stepped out towards the realization of our deliverables under this Open Access. In this reporting period, our consortium added a new tab named "Results", where one can find all the public deliverables of the project, as it is depicted below.

The screenshot shows the top navigation bar of the TheFSM website. The navigation bar is dark blue with white text. On the left is the TheFSM logo. To its right are the navigation links: Home, About, News & Events, Pilots, Results, and Contact. The 'Results' link is highlighted in white. Below the navigation bar, the page content is displayed on a light gray background. The first section is titled 'Foreseen outcomes' and contains a bulleted list of four items. The second section is titled 'Deliverables' and contains a sub-section 'WPI:Requirements' with a bulleted list of two items.

TheFSM The Food Safety Market

Home About News & Events Pilots **Results** Contact

Foreseen outcomes

- Specialize and adapt each one of the critical business scenarios to the local needs of food companies and their supply chain stakeholders.
- Ensure that they channel secure and trusted data through the platform.
- Establish a group of local stakeholders around each innovation pilot that will engage food companies and their supply chain stakeholders in each pilot.
- Implementation of each pilot in well calculated iterations that will gradually onboard actual clients and increase the volume of business that is executed through the platform.

Deliverables

WPI:Requirements

- [D1.1 - Report on Requirements_v1](#)
- [D1.1 - Report on Requirements_v2](#)

Regarding the dissemination of the scientific results and publications, **TheFSM** consortium has committed to the Horizon2020 Open Access mandates and has embraced all the appropriate measures to grant open access as known today. Gold Open Access, Green Open Access and self-archiving publishing methods are used. Open Access has a twofold objective, to ensure both the diffusion and the ease of access of the generated knowledge from the defined stakeholders, maximizing the impact coming from **TheFSM**. As such, the Consortium partners privilege Open Access journals or non-Open Access journals that support Green and Gold roads. They rely on dedicated funding from their research projects and/or institutions and store originals or pre-prints of their publications into their organization's repository (such as the PHAIDRA institutional repository of UNIVIE) and/or into OpenAIRE's Zenodo repository for publications. Similar strategies will be adopted for research data, whenever this may arise: Data repositories will be used for storing, managing and disseminating research data sets, in compliance with the requirements of the EC Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in H2020.

In case the journal has no option for Open Access, one of the options below must be performed by the beneficiary in order to ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results (online access for any user, free of charge):

- as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications. Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications;
- ensure open access to the deposited publication — via **TheFSM** website:
 - immediately upon publication if a free electronic version is available via the publisher; or
 - within six months of publication in any other case that involves delayed access.
- Ensure open access via the **TheFSM** website to the bibliographic metadata that identifies the scientific publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and include all of the following:

1. The terms "European Union (EU)" and "Horizon 2020";
2. The official name of the action, acronym and grant number;
3. The publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable;
4. A persistent identifier.

In general, each partner is responsible for complying with the regulations mentioned in the Grant Agreement and especially regarding Open Access. For example, the Coordinator of **TheFSM** project, Agroknow, is a standing contributor and advocate of Open Access to publicly funded information, actively participating and contributing to networks such as the GODAN initiative, the Interest Group on Agricultural Data (IGAD) of the Research Data Alliance (RDA), and the Global Food Safety Partnership (GFSP). It is a member of the Open Data Institute (ODI) and it has coordinated the Data Ecosystem WG of GODAN that investigated how public and private stakeholders can work together to catalyse the creation of a global data ecosystem for agriculture and food.

7.6 Foreseen Collaboration

One of the most challenging aspects of TheFSM project is to promote activities that will further enhance and facilitate the adoption of the platform, as well as the evolution of the business ecosystem around it. The key is not only the promotion of project's results or expertise of parties involved, but also the creation of links between the project and industry where its results may be applied.

Therefore, is crucial to: (i) design, execute and monitor a community engagement and partnership development strategy to help develop the ecosystem of data, services and users around the platform; (ii) develop and extend the appropriate partnerships that may ensure the commercial, community and technology partnerships that TheFSM should build upon to further grow.

We focus on specific activities such as:

- i. Being part of the software interoperability and data exchange groups that work in both agriculture and food IT systems (such as the AgriXchange initiative, the AOITI group, etc).
- ii. Making TheFSM a core part of the Trail Alliance for secure data exchange in the supply chain.
- iii. Participating and being visible in the European fora of relevance, such as EIT FOOD, the Big Data Value Association (BDVA), etc.
- iv. Becoming active members of the key associations working on food safety standards and mappings, such as the Global Food Safety Initiative (GFSI).
- v. Participating to European industrial associations such as the Food and Drink Europe, EuroCoop, COPA COGECA, etc.
- vi. Evolving further the collaboration with the US GMA in order to promote the platform to US companies and their supplier networks.
- vii. Connecting to user-driven communities such as the GROW observatory and other initiatives that link together small and very small agricultural suppliers that share farm data.

In order to provide a foundation for the execution of the partnership's development strategy a list with the potential communities and partners was distributed among TheFSM's partners. They were suggested to rate the relevance of the potential partners on a scale 1-4 (4-very relevant for the FSM; 1- minimal relevance to the FSM).

The table below indicates the EFSA as the most appropriate community for positioning the TheFSM platform.

No	COMMUNITIES	FIELD OF WORK	MARKET
1	EFSA - European Food Safety Authority	Agri-food initiative	Europe
2	GFSI - Global Food Safety Initiative	Agri-food initiative	Worldwide
3	COPA COGECA - European farmers EU agri-cooperatives	Agri-food initiative	Europe
4	IFOAM-OE	Agri-food initiative	Europe
5	BDVA - Big Data Value Association	Data exchange initiative	Europe
6	EIT FOOD	Agri-food initiative	Europe
7	Food and Drink Europe	Agri-food initiative	Europe
8	Safe Foods Corporation	Agri-food initiative	Worldwide
9	FMI The Food Industry Association	Agri-food initiative	N America
10	Trace Alliance	Supply chain initiative	Europe
11	CBA - Consumer Brand Association (former US GMA - Grocery Manufacturers Association)	Agri-food initiative	N America
12	AIOTI Group - Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation	Data exchange initiative	Europe
13	GOOD FOOD FOUNDATION	Agri-food initiative	N America
14	Weston A. Price Foundation	Agri-food initiative	N America

15	GROW Observatory	Data exchange initiative	Europe
16	EFFAT - European Federation of Trade Unions in the Food, Agriculture and Tourism	Agri-food initiative	Europe
17	EuroCoop - European Community of Consumer Cooperatives	Agri-food initiative	Europe
18	AgriXchange	Data exchange initiative	Worldwide

Table 11: Community and partnerships relevance results

7.7 Reporting on established partnerships

TheFSM project within already its first 18 months of operation, has achieved its membership into 3 related and considerable networks, namely:

1. **The Big Data Value Public-Private Partnership**, that aims to form a functional Data Market and Data Economy in Europe, in order to allow Europe to play a leading role in Big Data in the global market. The Big Data Value PPP is a partnership between the European Commission and the Big Data Value Association (BDVA).
2. **The Trace Alliance**, an EU based, non-profit association within the Origin Trial ecosystem that functions as an inclusive and collaborative hub, connecting organizations aiming to work together and solve complex supply chain challenges using blockchain technology. Every member that partners with the Trace Alliance benefits from the access that is given to new academic research papers and to knowledge resources. Moreover, direct access to use cases is granted along with access to new releases of technologies and solutions contributing to the member's promotion goals. Finally, a partnership with the Trace Alliance promotes the networking of the member offering enhanced visibility at Trace Alliance events along with the co-creation of a blockchain environment for supply chains and beyond.

Trace Alliance works with:

Enterprises

Companies that want to use the protocol for their supply chain challenges and are seeking rapid and effective solutions. This includes retail companies, manufacturers, logistics providers and other stakeholders.

Service Providers

Companies that provide supply chain management solutions and consulting or advisory services to help their clients be more efficient, and enhance product and consumer safety and brand protection.

Development Community

Individuals or groups of developers interested in building applications for supply chains on top of decentralized network capabilities, as well as improving the OriginTrail protocol core.

Research Institutions

Entities that have significant theoretical, empirical and research knowledge and can contribute to resolution of theoretical and practical challenges.

The Global Food Safety Initiative (GFSI), a network that connects the global food community with concerns regarding shared agreements of food safety. Its aim is to build consumers' trust in the food they buy no matter where it comes from and no matter where they live by improving food safety management practices. GFSI is also the one who decides on the measures for the food business facing ongoing certification disruption. Agroknow, the coordinator of TheFSM project has already paved the way for the project's participation and representation at the GFSI Conference that took place in March 2021, where over 1.200 food industry leaders from 50+ countries attended, making the Conference the meeting place for decision-makers from across the supply chain. Participants shared knowledge, strengthen their networks and showcase their learnings and business.

8. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE PLANS

8.1. Conclusion

In the current document we presented the achievements and outcomes of the TheFSM project for the first 18 months of its implementation. Especially, a description of business scenarios, business requirements grouped in users' stories and the results per business scenario were showcased. Based on the requirements, and with the adoption of an agile iterative development process, the three applications, namely Food Inspector, FOODAKAI 2.0 and Agrivi 2.0, consisting the TheFSM platform were further developed and updated. In section 4 of this report, we presented the technological stack and infrastructure for the first version of TheFSM platform and the prototype version of the platform. Section 5 includes the low fidelity mockups of TheFSM Data Market Place, followed by high fidelity mockups which guided the development of the platform UIs. A short description of pilot groups, pilot sites and pilot schedule were presented in section 6, while section 7 documents the various dissemination, awareness and outreach activities and results from M01-M18.

8.2. Future Plans

The next version of this document is projected to integrate the next steps until the end of the project (M36). Next steps to achieve the proper execution of TheFSM project include:

- Incorporation of updated requirements to the application prototypes-decision regarding the certification standards which will be included in inspection tool.
- Creation of monitoring methodology/tool regarding the fulfilment of BRs, TRs, LR & DRs through the functionalities of the platform & applications.
- Continuous update of the requirements according technical requirements of the platform, legal and data issues.
- Connection of focus groups with the implementation of the first cycle of pilots.
- Start the pilot's iteration in the final quarter of 2021.
- The UI developed for the demonstrator will be updated and replaced with the final UI adopted by TheFSM Platform, developed within the tasks of TheFSM Data Marketplace.
- Continue the iterative development process that was developed in the context of TheFSM project to update the three applications and their interconnection to the TheFSM platform.
- Translate and localize the TheFSM platform.
- Provide updated detailed sequence diagrams and interaction flows that prove the promised functionality as more interaction flows and use cases are covered.
- Future dissemination and communication actions are predicted to be implemented, focusing on the expansion of the pilots results and the diffusion of TheFSM Data Platform, informing all the key stakeholders and the general public.